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CABANATUAN CITY

**LEADERSHIP MENTORING PROGRAM
FOR THE NORTHEAST PANGASINAN DISTRICT
UNITED METHODIST YOUTH FELLOWSHIP**

A Thesis Presented to the
Faculty of Graduate School
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In Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree
Master of Arts in Christian Education

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APPROVAL SHEET

This master thesis entitled **LEADERSHIP MENTORING PROGRAM FOR THE NORTHEAST PANGASINAN DISTRICT UNITED METHODIST YOUTH FELLOWSHIP**, prepared and submitted by Rev. Cesar Taqueban Reyes, Jr., in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Degree Master of Arts in Christian Education (MACE) has been read and it's recommended for acceptance and approval for oral examination.

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To God be all the praises and glory, now and forever!

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DEDICATION

The whole research and work is dedicated to God as an instrument to further His ministry through the United Methodist Church in helping people grow and develop more as a living witnesses of the gospel, and as leaders of the future who follows the steps of Christ, in knowing Him and in making Him known.

ABSTRACT

TITLE: LEADERSHIP MENTORING PROGRAM FOR THE
NORTHEAST PANGASINAN DISTRICT UNITED
METHODIST YOUTH FELLOWSHIP

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The United Methodist Youth Fellowship is an integral ministerial arm of the United Methodist Church. It is an organization engaged in different ministries. One of the prominent ministries of the UMYF is the leadership development of the young people as seen in Bible Study training, Christmas and Summer Institutes, Conferences, and quarterly meetings. Leadership is crucial not only in organization but also as an individual. The study determined to address the leadership insufficiencies of the NEPD UMYF by having an assessment on their leadership needs, and design a leadership mentoring training module to help the UMYF leadership holistically and become better in their own dealings.

The main instrument in assessing the leadership needs was the Quantitative-Descriptive method through the Questionnaire-Checklist. One hundred sixty (160)

respondents were involved in this study, 154 UMYF and 6 Adults who were formerly officers.

The leadership needs assessment had shown that there was a need for the following categories; 1st rank was Spiritual Development with a weighted mean of 3.17, verbally interpreted as needed. Under this category are prayer life, church ministry involvement, daily devotion & bible reading, and witness; 2nd rank was Personality Development with a weighted mean of 3.16, verbally interpreted as needed. Under this category are positive attitude, social manner and behavior, hygiene, and dress code; rank 3rd was Communication Skills with a weighted mean of 3.07, verbally interpreted as needed. Under this category are active listening, organization of thoughts and participation during meeting, fluency and proficiency in speaking, writing skills; 4th rank was Leadership Abilities with a weighted mean of 3.04, verbally interpreted as needed. Under this category are building relationship, planning, collaboration, execution and implementation, persuasion; and 5th rank was Other Skills with a weighted mean of 3.01, verbally interpreted as needed. Under this category are time management, knowledge with the organization, knowledge with the legal aspects and church discipline, conflict resolution and financial management.

The output of this study was to design a leadership mentoring training module to address the leadership needs based on the assessment. The material is expected to help leaders to grow and be developed more, and make the leadership transition better through mentoring.

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CHAPTER 1

THE PROBLEM AND ITS SETTING

Introduction

The United Methodist Youth Fellowship (UMYF) is a lay organization which is active in church ministerial participation from local to national level in the Philippines. Any United Methodist Church (UMC) member that is within the range of 12 to 23 is considered a member of the UMYF organization in the country. UMYF is equipped with multitude of programs and activities not only for the young people of the church but also include other ministries like Children ministry, sociocultural exposure, community involvement, and social and environmental awareness. The supreme task of the UMYF is to know Christ and make Him known. In achieving the task of ‘knowing Christ’, certain activities are held that focus on the development of young people in terms of personality, character, leadership, and spirituality. In the task of ‘making Him known’, it is usually centered on discipleship, witnessing, team building, and ministerial engaging. Being involved in the UMYF organization means a total development that aims not just to strengthen the organization but also to uplift each young people to reach the zenith of an individual’s potential as a person that would fulfill his or her purpose given by God.

Leadership is considered a basic idea that every UMYF who holds a position in any level understands. If that is so, then what could be the reason on why the UMYF leadership is not consistent? As leaders are being changed, programs, activities, and strategies also change. One of the many observations of the researcher is that whenever

an officer is replaced by others, he or she does not involve him or herself as much as possible anymore for the reason of giving others the chance to experience what the previous officer had experienced. The result of this action is the inconsistencies inside of the same organization, the UMYF, going through the same problems and conflicts over and over again, and history just repeats itself. Another observation of the researcher is lack of mentors, who, supposedly be guiding the younger generation of the UMYF.

Mentoring is a process in which an experienced individual helps another person develop his or her goals and skills through a series of time-limited, confidential, one-on-one conversations and other learning activities. Mentors also draw benefits from the mentoring relationship. As a mentor, he or she will have the opportunity to share his or her wisdom and experiences, evolve his or her own thinking, develop a new relationship, and deepen his or her skills as a mentor.¹ Leadership is not an exclusive club for those who were born with it. Leadership is developed, not discovered. The truly born leader will always emerge; but, to stay on top, natural leadership characteristics must be developed.² Through mentoring, the growth and development of the NEPD UMYF organization as a whole in the long run can be achieved not only for the benefit of the mentees but including the whole UMC as well.

¹Center for Health Leadership & Practice, *Mentoring Guide: A Guide for Mentors* (Oakland, CA: Center for Health Leadership & Practice, Public Health Institute 2003), 1.

²John C. Maxwell, *Ultimate Leadership: Maximize Your Potential and Empower Your Team* (Nashville, TN: Thomas Nelson, 2007), 244-247.

In NEPD, there is no mentoring program designed for the UMYF.³ This fact became one of the considerations that the researcher would want to address, and to propose a program specifically targeting the UMYF officers of both district and local level in NEPD. In this manner, it is the researcher’s intention to provide support on the growth and development of the UMYF organization in Northeast Pangasinan District (NEPD) under Northwest Philippines Annual Conference (NWPAC), through Leadership Mentoring Program, the focus of this research.

Statement of the Problem

When someone says leadership in the UMYF context, it means church ministerial participation (being active inside the church) and holding an office (duly elected UMYF based on UMYF Constitution). This limitation suffocates the potential of a youth because of the “do your responsibilities” paradigm. Instead of the youth moving in a positive manner through learning, the person is hindered because of the persecution being received whenever he or she is failing in doing the leadership responsibility. Determining the individual leadership needs of a UMYF will help in addressing this kind of leadership problem which causes the UMYF to struggle in their leadership responsibilities. In this situation, the researcher studied the leadership needs of the UMYF of both the local and district levels in NEPD by answering the following question:

1. What was the UMYF assessment of leadership needs in terms of:
 - a. personality development;

³Based on the NEPD District Superintendent Reports 2012-2017. According to the DS Rev. Buson Valdez of NEPD there are instances of mentoring but not as a program, rather an initiative of some Church Workers and Lay Persons in their own respective local churches.

-
- b. communication Skills;
 - c. leadership abilities;
 - d. other skills; and
 - e. spiritual formation;
2. How did the respondents reveal other needs to enhance and develop their leadership skills?
 3. What module was designed to meet the leadership needs of the youth?

Conceptual Framework

The researcher modeled the following figure in determining the leadership needs of the NEPD UMYF District and Local Church Officers as a basis for the leadership mentoring program through a module with a training material as the final product.

Figure 1. Conceptual Model

This research assessed the leadership needs of the District and Local UMYF Officers in Northeast Pangasinan District (NEPD) in terms of Personality development, Communication skills, Leadership abilities, Other skills, and Spiritual formation. Upon assessment, a leadership training program was designed through a module. The module was based on the assessment of leadership needs if it is either ‘needed’ or ‘highly needed’.

Significance of the Study

The purpose of this research was to design a leadership mentoring program that focused on the leadership needs of the NEPD UMYF Officers both in district and local levels. The idea behind the research was to help the UMYF leaders and officers to learn, grow, and develop more not just as an individual but also as leaders modeled after Christ. The Leadership Mentoring Program will guide the UMYF as he or she engages as an officer in the UMYF organization. The program’s capability will not be limited to the church paradigm alone, but can also be helpful in their schools, workplaces, businesses, and local community. It will help the individual to unleash his or her full potential in whatever work he or she is doing. It will enable him or her to realize the talents, gifts, and even his or her purpose in life. The person will learn to take control of the spiritual, mental, emotional, physical, and financial aspects of his or her life, to awaken the giant within.⁴

⁴ Anthony Robbins, *Awaken the Giant within How to Take Immediate Control of Your Mental, Emotional, Physical & Financial Destiny!* (New York: Simon & Schuster Paperbacks, 2013).

Scope and Limitation of the Study

This research was conducted to determine the need for leadership mentoring program of the NEPD UMYF Officers. The leadership needs of the NEPD UMYF officers was the basis for the leadership mentoring program. The research will cover the Northeast Pangasinan District UMYF Officers in both district and local levels in 18 churches. There will be a total of 160 respondents, composed of current and past UMYF leaders. The order of priority for the respondents were as follows: The first priority was the current UMYF elected officer 2018-2019; The second priority was the past UMYF officers who are still in the UMYF age range (12-23); and the last priority was the past UMYF officers regardless of age.

Definition of Terms

The following terminologies were defined based on the observable characteristics and how it was used in the study to have a better understanding.

- | | | |
|----------------------|---|--|
| Communication Skills | - | Refers to the UMYF's ability to establish a connection towards other. It may be in the form of verbal or writing. |
| District Level | - | A higher level in the UMC church structure hierarchy next to the local church level. The district is usually led by the District Superintendent (DS).
The current DS of NEPD is Rev. Buson P. Valdez. |

-
- | | | |
|----------------------|---|--|
| Leader | - | An elected UMYF officer holding a position in the UMYF organization in local, district, annual, and national levels. |
| Leadership Abilities | - | This refer to the UMYF’s capability in planning and execution, collaboration with co-officers, teamwork, and building relationship with the whole organization. |
| Local Level | - | The grass root level of the UMC. This level means that the church is already established, self-sufficient, and assists the district through financial obligations and activity participation. |
| Mentor | - | The person who teaches and trains a UMYF Officer / Leader. |
| NEPD | - | Northeast Pangasinan District. Composed of 19 Local churches and 3 mission congregations. It is located on the eastern part of Pangasinan. |
| NWPAC | - | Northwest Philippines Annual Conference. This is the conference where the NEPD is located. Annual conference is the next level after the district. The Bishop is the one presiding in annual conferences. There are 26 UMC Annual Conferences in the entire Philippines. |

-
- Other Skills - This refer to the UMYF’s capacity to manage finances, time, conflict, including the knowledge in legal aspects, church discipline, and organization.
- Personality Development - This refers to the UMYF’s hygiene, dressing well, social manner and behavior, confidence, and having a positive attitude in all situations.
- Spiritual Formation - This refers to the UMYF’s spiritual life in terms of prayer, witnessing, church ministry, integrity, and devotion.
- UMYF - United Methodist Youth Fellowship is the official youth organization of the United Methodist Church in the Philippines. All UMC members who are in the age range of 12 to 23 are considered as a UMYF. The UMYF is the most active lay organization in the UMC ministry.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

This chapter provides the information regarding the concept of leadership, leadership context and paradigm in the United Methodist Youth Fellowship (UMYF), historical background of the UMYF including its mission and vision, leadership branches like personality development, and the biblical foundation of leadership.

UMC Seminaries in the Philippines impart a general information regarding ministries as a whole in their courses like the Master of Divinity program. Unlike the secular courses which have specialized fields, the students in UMC Seminaries are encouraged to learn more and pursue higher education based on the chosen field of specialization that would support the ministry of interest. With this reason, there are many strategies being created by different church workers to encourage members like the young people. As part of their strategy, the liturgical service is changed into contemporary which is the worship style of the younger generation. Others hold many activities that would enable new young people to meet and greet one another. Today, we have a reason to believe that the youth, the UMYF, is the future not only of a nation but also of the United Methodist Church for which the UMYF is the official youth organization of the UMC in the Philippines. Its roots are traced from the organization of the Epworth League in the Philippines in 1901. In 1941, the Methodist Youth Fellowship

was presented and adopted at the 2nd National Conference of the Epworth League. By 1945, a constitution was ratified.⁵

The Young People

Many generations of young people between the ages of 15 and 24 have already passed, and more is yet to come. Each generation is so unique most especially in the issues that every generation is facing. These issues always remain as a primary concern for the society. Even though the generation of the young people is changing at a rapid pace, the basic aspects of their lives remain the same. Education, health, application to work, family formation, and productive and responsible citizenship are still among the topmost priorities of these young people. The transition period from youth to adulthood of each generation also differs. There is the effect of rapid globalization, spread of deadly diseases like HIV/AIDS, the enormous amount of information and communication technology, and other developments that affect the living of young people. There are cases that some generation of young people in the past are living in a period of global ideological polarization. As time goes by, their participation in different institutions became more intense which influences their social involvement particularly in democratic decision-making processes, minimizing the former ideological focus and being replaced by new ideological conflicts. This type of historical perspective must stay as a reminder for the society that the young people of today's generation is different from the past generations. It is essential that these young people's intervention remain relevant and

⁵ Earlie L. Pasion, *The Wave* Master's Thesis, Wesley Divinity School, Wesleyan University Philippines, Cabanatuan 2013, 8.

valid for the current young generation in society, and not modeled in the realities of the past. According to the World Programme of Action for Youth to the Year 2000 and Beyond, adopted by the General Assembly in its resolution 50/81 of 1995, the ten priority areas in dealing with the life aspects of a youth are the following; (1) Education; (2) Employment; (3) Hunger and poverty; (4) Health; (5) Environment; (6) Drug abuse; (7) Juvenile delinquency; (8) Leisure activities; (9) Young women; (10) Participation of Young People in decision-making. Five additional priority areas identified by the General Assembly in its resolution 58/133 of 2003 are as follows; (1) Globalization; (2) Information and communication technology; (3) HIV/AIDS; (4) Youth and armed conflict; (5) Intergenerational relations. The life aspects of the youth were then summarized based on the result of the analysis into; Poverty. The estimated, according to poverty data from 2002, that some 209 million and 515 million youth live on less than US\$ 1 and US\$ 2 per day respectively; Education. Since 1995, the number of children completing primary school is increasing rapidly including the tertiary level. According to the data, there are four out of five youth in the secondary school while the estimated number for Tertiary level is at 100 million engaged in studies worldwide. However, there are atleast 113 million children that are not attending school, and atleast 130 million youth who are considered illiterate; Employment. Even though there is a massive progress in the art of academic achievement, unemployment has reached a number of atleast 88 million in which youth are the ones greatly affected. Unemployment of young people are numerous in Western Asia, North Africa and sub-Saharan Africa; Health. The rate of premarital sex is rising in an exploding manner around the globe most especially

in the Philippines. In consideration to this, there is also the rise of HIV/AIDS and is the primary cause of mortality among the young people; Environment. Environmental awareness is very much needed in today's generation. The youth must continually engage themselves to the society's decision-making process concerning the environment for a sustainable future; Leisure. Leisure time for the young people play a vital role in terms of social inclusion, opportunities, and overall development. The youth today are constantly engage in searching for new ways to utilize their free time both for recreational and necessary activities; Drug abuse. The use of illegal drugs is now becoming more rampant than ever before. The young people usually take the method of drugs to escape the reality of life brought by the societies' pressure, resulting to anxieties and depression; Globalization. Young people can easily adapt and can utilize the opportunities brought by globalization. However, the negative effect lies most especially in the developing countries which are not used to globalization yet and are being taken advantage of. Globalization affects the youth in terms of employment opportunities, large numbers of young people have not benefited from this process, especially in developing countries. Globalization has had an impact on youth employment opportunities and migration patterns, and has led to profound changes in youth culture and consumerism and in global youth citizenship and activism.⁶

⁶ *World Youth Report 2005* (New York: United Nations, Dept. of Economic and Social Affairs, 2005), 2-7.

The United Methodist Youth Fellowship

The Methodist Youth Fellowship was formed during the Watch Night Service held on December 31, 1941 from the three (3) youth groups from the Methodist Protestant Church, South Methodist Episcopal Church, and the Methodist Episcopal Church. On May 15, 1889, the Epworth League of The Methodist Episcopal Church was founded at Central Methodist Episcopal Church (now Epworth-Euclid Methodist Church) in Cleveland, Ohio. In 1889, a group of young people's societies in the Methodist Episcopal Church South was organized into a cooperative union. The General Conference of the Methodist Episcopal Church South held at Saint Louis Missouri in 1890 responded to a resolution that had been sent by the Trinity Methodist Episcopal Church South of Los Angeles, California to authorize the formation of Epworth League of the Methodist Episcopal Church South. The Board of Education set up a youth commission to conduct a careful study and make recommendations for this unified program. The decision was made to name the new youth movement called the Methodist Youth Fellowship.⁷

The proposed constitution was approved and ratified which led to the organization of local, district and conference levels. The first Methodist Youth National Conference was held Guimba, Nueva Ecija on January 2-5, 1951 led by Rev. F.V. Cabotaje, the Executive Secretary of the Central Conference Board of Education during those times. La Verne Mercado was the first elected National MYF President which attended by three hundred (300) delegates. The organization soon became the United Methodist Youth Fellowship in the Philippines (UMYFP). The 14th UMYFP Convention held on March

⁷ Butch A. Paculan, *The Essence of UMYF Ministry* Master's Thesis, Wesley Divinity School, Wesleyan University Philippines, Cabanatuan 2016, 9-11.

1976 formally adopted the new constitution. Rogelio Bueno was elected as President for the third time. The new constitution and By-Laws was amended by the Constitutional Drafting Committee created on 1982, at the 17th Biennial Convention. A formal call to hold a Constitutional Convention (ConCon) was done at Iba, Zambales in April 2006 during the 29th National Youth Conference (NYC). The ConCon took place at Malolos, Bulacan in July 2007 presidency of Mighty Rasing.⁸

In the ministerial concept of UMYF leadership, there is nothing new about it. UMYF leaders are always given much responsibility that serves as their training, but whenever a UMYF cannot do his or her responsibility as an officer, he or she is immediately persecuted. Failure to finish something is often treated as a bad thing whatever the reasons are, an idea prominent in UMC society. In leadership, failure is a must. It is an idea that must be undergone by a leader to grow, learn, and develop more. Sometimes it is forgotten that the UMYF Leaders are all voluntary, which means they do not receive monthly allowance or even funding in a personal basis. But through persecution, including their own problems in schools or families, the tendency for them to leave the church is almost certain. UMYF Leaders bear much responsibility that is not proportional to their emotional and cognitive intelligences, level of maturity, and strength of character, when it comes to leading. This is where Leadership Mentoring Program will take its place. Mentorship aims to guide, teach, and train a person into realizing his or her full potential and using it for the betterment of the society. It is not exclusive to the person's life rather it is for the rendering of service to others. Leadership Mentoring is

⁸ NYC: *On the Pages of UMYFP History*, UMYFP Pananaw, accessed September 27, 2018, <https://umyfpnanaw.wordpress.com/tag/national/>.

about helping a person to pursue excellence in service, character, and faith, in taking part in the transformation of the world as servants of God.

Leadership

Leadership is a concept which is often talked about, and which has generated a rapid spread of literature in the field of management and organizational sciences. Despite the accepted paradigm on the importance of leadership for the success of both private and public sector organizations and institutions, studies on leadership is not successful in creating a comprehensive model and approach which would be acceptable with the scholars and practitioners. There is no consistent and fixed meaning about leadership. Leadership is defined by others based on the developmental context. Leadership differs as depending on the context of the organization and institution involved. Studying leadership is greatly dominated by scholars and practitioners involved in management and organizational sciences, but not a total concern of political scientist, economists, and development theorists. The majority of conceptions in terms of leadership today are mostly Western-oriented, Universalist or individualistic. Aside from the importance of leadership for growth and development, analysis of leadership in practice is given a little concern. The Leaders, Elites and Coalitions Research Programme (LECRP) has concluded that leadership should also be understood in a political sense including the process that involves three critical aspects; (1) Leadership is the logistics of an organization which is the mobilization of people and resources (economic, political and other) in achieving a particular goal; (2) Leadership must be seen in the context of power,

authority and legitimacy, guided by history, institutions, goals and political culture; (3) Leadership is associated in making a formal or informal union of leaders and elites, to provide solutions to problems and challenges that would lead to growth and development.⁹

Leadership ability is the lid that determines a person's effectiveness in leadership. If the person's lid or his ability to lead is low, then the potential to lead is also low. When the lid is high, the potential effectiveness of the person is also high, i.e. if a person's leadership effectiveness rates an eight out of ten, then his effectiveness can never be greater than a seven. If the person's leadership is only four (4), then his effectiveness will be no higher than three (3). Leadership ability determines the effectiveness and the potential impact. It is the lid towards personal and organizational effectiveness. If there is a strong leadership, then the lid is high. In contrast, if it is not or in a low level, then the organization is limited. That is one reason on why organizations look for new leadership when they get into trouble. Becoming a leader is similar to investing successfully in the stock market. If someone's goal is to get rich in a day, then the person will not be successful. The primary factor is the discipline in a daily basis for a long term that would make the greatest difference. The same thing happens in leadership, there must be a daily training and discipline in a long run to achieve a satisfactory result. Leadership develops daily and not in a day. Many people do not understand the value of leadership. They believe that leadership is only for the elites – for the people holding high positions in private and public sectors. Opportunities then are being wasted because of such thinking. When someone recognizes that he or she lacks the skill and began to have a daily

⁹ Lyne de Ver, H. (2009), *Conceptions of Leadership*, Background Paper 4, 3.

discipline of personal growth in leadership, big things will come. Leadership ability is not static. For someone who is willing to invest in leadership will surely grow and gets better in life.¹⁰

Personality Development

Personality is a pattern of thoughts, feelings, and behaviors that uniquely distinguishes one person from another. It is the combination of all learnt behavior which forms the person's particular responses to environmental and societal factors. The five-factor model (FFM) is based on common language labels of personality. These labels are organized through factor analysis which is not, in any form, a scientific experiment. Theory presented five broad dimensions utilized by some psychologists in making a description regarding human personality and psyche. The five factors have been identified as openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism (OCEAN) and they represent the foundational structure of personality traits.¹¹

¹⁰ Maxwell, John C. *The Complete 101 Collection: What Every Leader Needs to Know; Attitude, Relationships, Equipping, Leadership, Mentoring and Success*. Nashville, TN: Thomas Nelson, 2015.151-162.

¹¹ M. GOPIKRISHNAN, *A Course in Personality Development*, accessed September 29, 2018, https://www.bharathuniv.ac.in/colleges1/downloads/courseware_ece/notes/BSS201 - PERSONALITY.pdf.

Table 1. Five Factor Model Of Personality

Dimension of Personality	High Level	Low Level
Openness to experience	Inventive, Curious	Cautious, Conservative
Conscientiousness	Efficient, Organized,	Easy going, Careless
Extraversion	Outgoing, Energetic	Solitary, Reserved
Agreeableness	Friendly, Compassionate	Competitive, Outspoken
Neuroticism	Sensitive, Nervous	Secure, Confident

Personality development includes activities for the development of awareness, identity, talents, human potential, human capital, employability, quality of life, and contribution to the realization of dreams and aspirations, engaging in activities that lead people in the role of leaders, guides, teachers, and managers for them to realize their full potential. Personal development in institutions corresponds to the methods, programs, tools, techniques, and assessment systems that support human development individually in an organization. The scope of personality development includes knowing how to dress well, social graces, grooming, speech and interpersonal skills. Some of the key benefits of developing your personality include the following; (1) Confidence. Through personality development, a person could gain confidence. When you know you are groomed and dressed well, this makes a person less anxious when meeting a person. Knowing the right words to say and how to properly conduct someone's self will increase his or her confidence; (2) Credibility. Personality development makes people more

credible. Knowing what to wear and being aware of other aspects of enhancing physical features will add to the person's credibility; (3) Interaction. Personality development encourages people to interact with others. Hygiene and social behavior plays an important role in having a successful interaction toward others; (4) Leading and Motivating. Personality development helps to increase the person's capacity in leading and motivating. A person who has a winning attitude will be better in motivating. People are less likely to get bored, and our ideas will have more impact and credibility. A person can lead better if he or she projects an aura of confidence and credibility; (5) Curiosity. A wrong word if used can ruin relationships. Knowing the right things to say shows both respect and intellectual sophistication because a single wrong word can destroy the conversation's momentum. The best case is when someone is having an interaction with a foreigner. Culture and tradition plays a role in such interaction. Raising the ability of curiosity will avoid complicated communication; (6) Communication skills. Personality development improves communication skills. People are more receptive to what is being said if people are impressed with someone's personality. Verbal communication skills are also part of personality development; improving a person's speech will strengthen the impact of the message. A person cannot win by talent and hard work alone. Personality development is a crucial ingredient that everyone must obtain. Most of the people who are models of great personality have taken a lot of effort in developing their natural features.¹²

¹² *Ibid*

Communication Skills

The communication process in an organization connects all the members of an institution including the external environment. The job of the person with highest position is to securely make a link every resource the institution has, through proper communication. Without the proper element of communication, the capacity to achieve a certain goal in an institution will be next to impossibility most especially if the goal requires teamwork. Communication involves the transfer and exchanging of ideas, information, human emotions, etc. The concept of communication is common understanding between the involved parties, the Sender and Receiver, about what is being communicated called the Message. Message includes ideas, data, statistics, emotions, and feelings. According to the studies, people spend 40 to 60% of time on communication. As a person's position in the organizational hierarchy is going higher, he or she needs to spend more time than the average in communicating. The head of any organization may be expected to spend more than 80% of his or her time on communication. The time being spent in communication will lead to the effectivity, efficiency, creativity and productivity of the person leading an organization. The communication process in any organization is so important in achieving its objectives. The management of communication system in an organization has a great impact on the overall effectiveness of the whole organization. There are many barriers that can disrupt the process of communication that may result to a breakdown. Some of the common barriers to effective communication are the following: (1) Transmission Alterations. This is the change on the original message being sent caused by alterations consciously or unconsciously, factored

by individual differences of the people sending the message in a chain. These differences include cultural background, social class, educational level, age group, experience etc. One effective way to minimize alterations would be to ask the receiver to repeat what he or she has understood. The sender then would be able to correct mistakes immediately if the received message is unclear. Either the sender or the receiver can make the effort of correcting one another for message clarity;

(2) Physical Limitations. The difference between perception and reality may be termed perceptual error. The sensory limitations (sight, sound, touch, taste and smell) restrict perceptual clarity;

(3) Inattention. The receiver should give proper attention to the message being received. The sender should be attentive if the receiver is giving enough attention to what the sender will relay, and give the message only if the receiver is attentive enough to understand clearly. Despite physical proximity with the sender, the receiver's level of attention may come down or his or her thoughts may take side excursions while the sender is talking. The sender should recognize this as a natural and normal phenomenon and make efforts to regain receivers' attention at periodic intervals;

(4) Selective Listening. Selective perception may happen if the receiver tries to remove some of the information when it is contradictory to what he or she believes. Selective perception often happens due to difference and conflicting interests;

(5) Mistrust of the Source. When there is an engagement between the same sender and receiver over time, the receiver at some point develops trust and confidence regarding the words of the sender. It may be termed source credibility. To be an effective communicator, one should develop himself or herself as a credible source of information;

(6) Exaggeration. People may resort to exaggeration to

dramatize ones presentation or to make it more attractive, humorous etc. However, in the long run, one who is known to exaggerate always loses credibility: (7) Distortion. Distortion on the original message may be committed intentionally or unintentionally which brings undesirable and even harmful result: (8) Uniqueness. Because of the uniqueness of individuals, their experiences, and as a result of this, their perceptions differ: (9) Badly Expressed Messages. If the sender is not prepared, inadequate of the instrument, and even the mannerism of the sender can express messages in bad setting which will not deliver the right meaning of the message, that also includes wrong punctuation, pronunciation, grammar etc.: (10) Unclarified Assumptions. Assumptions are easily made based on what a person hears, sees, or reads, which may have no relation to reality. When one makes decisions or takes action based on wrong assumptions, the result will be disastrous: (11) Abstractions. Abstracting is the process of deriving meaning that enables people to give emphasis to different factors. Because of this, different people, when bombarded with the same stimulus or set of stimuli, may give different responses based on different conclusions: (12) Absentmindedness. A strong barrier than can really affect effective communication is absentmindedness. The receiver should give proper attention and involvement to the message of the sender: (13) Time Pressure: People in positions of authority and responsibility may not have enough time to communicate with everybody. Insufficiency of communication can be caused by time pressure which can lead to people being left out of the formal channel or discussion through communication.¹³

¹³ Sreedhar, C. & Oommen, M. *Training Module On Personality Development*. Accessed September 29,

There is no fixed method for ensuring an effective organizational communication because of its complex process. However, organizational communication can be improved. First, the message must be improved including the understanding of the people communicating. The following are some techniques that will aid in the improvement of communication; (1) Receiver Orientation. Considering the language of the receiver is a way in improving communication. Care should be taken to use words and usages that suit the listener's intelligence and background; (2) Attention to the ABCs: As a guiding principle for effective communication it should always be remembered to give proper attention to the ABCs (attractiveness, brevity and clarity); (3) Appropriateness. Appropriateness in communication means a lot of things. Communication must be taken in the proper context, just enough to convey a message with clarity; (4) Use of Humor. Communication is a process which involves many functions to enable a smooth operation. Humor is an effective component of communication, but be aware that humor is not proper all the time and may result to negative result if misused; (5) Use of Right Appeal: Using a right appeal will greatly improve the effectiveness of communication. The skill of the communicator lies in identifying the right appeal for each situation and its utilization; (6) Repetition. The universally acknowledged principle of learning; repetition can greatly contribute to communication effectiveness. Repetition will ensure that even if one part of the message is not understood, there are other parts, which will carry the same meaning; (7) Effective Timing. A host of message competes for people's attention simultaneously. Due to the number of messages being received, many of them are not

decoded or received properly. Message flow through proper timing is important and should be in order to avoid complications and overlapping messages; (8) Simplifying Language. Use of complicated language hinders effective communication. Effective communication involves transmitting clearly to be understood. (9) Effective Listening. Effective listening and effective speaker are both important to communication process. Communicators must able to express themselves clearly and understand the people they are communicating with. By proper listening, one can encourage other to express true feelings, hopes, aspirations and emotions. Listening to understand is required.¹⁴

Leadership Abilities

John Maxwell's "The 21 Irrefutable Laws of Leadership" is a book that contains helpful insights regarding leadership abilities. John Maxwell presented 21 common principles or laws that were considered universally true regardless of culture or society; (1) THE LAW OF THE LID. The lid determines the person's leadership effectiveness. Leadership effectiveness is directly proportional to the level of lid. The higher the lid, the higher the effectiveness. Leadership skills and abilities are also affected by the lid. The lid should be a guide to a person to check on what ability or skill should he or she must improve, and aim that the lid must increase its level always for the betterment of leadership; (2) THE LAW OF INFLUENCE. Leadership is influence. In order to be an effective leader, a person must have a positive influence toward his or her teammates to be able to work in a smooth give and take relationship. The best leaders understand that

¹⁴ *Ibid*

helping people to reach their potential is the true definition of leadership, even if those people will become better than these leaders. Leadership is not determined by having a title (i.e. CEO, Pastor, Director, Manager); (3) THE LAW OF PROCESS. Leadership develops daily and not in a day. Daily habits and discipline are important factors into developing one's leadership skills including priorities, passion, abilities, relationships, attitude, personal disciplines, vision, and influence. As a leader, one must have a leader's growth plan to himself or herself, and also as someone who leads, he or she have to set the course of others into success as well; (4) THE LAW OF NAVIGATION. Once the process has been set to a certain direction, the next is to navigate properly an organization or the team through hindrances, challenges and obstacles to successfully reach the desired goal. Leaders try to learn from the past experiences and hurtful failures, and then look ahead to see where conflict and challenge may arise. With all of these in mind, leaders will preemptively respond according to those challenges as they move forward toward the goal, to fulfill the vision; (5) THE LAW OF ADDITION. Adding value to others and intentionally making them valuable. It is important that we build relationship to the team being finding out their priorities, goals, hopes, and dreams, and then figuring out what the leader can do to assist them in getting where they need to go; (6) THE LAW OF SOLID GROUND. The solid ground of leadership is trust. Building trust is one of the greatest challenge leaders' face in our century, especially those who are involved in ministerial work. Trust is a fragile matter because it has been always abused by self-serving leaders. Trust is a crucial matter in leadership. Trust is built through consistent demonstration of competence, connection, and character. Trust is affected by sound decision making,

admitting mistakes and failures, and by putting the whole team ahead of the leader; (7) THE LAW OF RESPECT. People usually follow leaders who are stronger than themselves. Reliance on talent alone will not be enough and a great pitfall for leaders, for good leaders rely on respect from others. When people respect shows respect, that is admiration. When people respect someone as a friend that is love. When people respect someone as a leader, they will follow; (8) THE LAW OF INTUITION. Intuition is possessed by every person. People are usually intuitive in their area of strength. Through intuition, leaders evaluate everything with a leadership bias. The Law of Intuition then is the evaluation of something based on facts, instincts, and other factors which include the team's morale, momentum of organization, and relationship with others. Intuition might be the hardest leadership skill to develop. Its reliance is more than just leadership experience. Natural aptitude of having a bird's eye view of all the factors at once and the ability to naturally discern possible actions and outcomes is also a part of it. Intuitive leaders tune-in to leadership dynamics. Many leaders see this as an ability to 'smell' things in their organization. They can sense people's attitudes and the chemistry of the whole team. They have the capacity to know situation and the facts behind it. That is the result of their leadership intuition; (9) THE LAW OF MAGNETISM. A person attracts people like himself or herself. It is the "who you are is who you attract." This is helpful in knowing a person's weaknesses and seeking to improve. Leaders help to shape the culture of their organizations based on who they are and what they do. The personality and character traits of a person will be a huge factor in attracting other people with the same personality and character traits. Therefore, it is necessary for a leader to grow more

and taking the next level further so that he or she could attract people who are also willing to grow like him or her, in doing so, the whole team or organization will grow as well; (10) THE LAW OF CONNECTION. Building relationship and connection first is the key in developing good credibility. A leader must help his or her team first before asking for help. In that way, the team would know that their leader is truly sincere and shows care to them. This will result to better teamwork, excellent camaraderie, and people would not be having a hard time catching up the vision of the leader. Relationship is crucial in any organization or institution to achieve success; (11) THE LAW OF THE INNER CIRCLE. A leader's potential is affected by those who is closest to him or her. To leverage the law of the inner circle then, a leader must surround him or herself continually with people who show admiration and respect, and those who wanted growth in their lives. The leader must also increase in capacity and maximize his or her potential as leader, and aiming to be the best leader he or she can be; (12) THE LAW OF EMPOWERMENT. Secure leaders give power to others. Secure leaders spend their time identifying other leaders and building them up. Insecure leaders are always suspicious and careful about the people around them. They do not want that others would get better than these insecure leaders and they undermine the people's potential and growth. Empowerment and enlarging others is a powerful not only for the person being developed but also for the mentor or leader; (13) THE LAW OF THE PICTURE. When a leader shows the way with right actions, his or her followers copy them and succeed. Integrity is a vital part in this law. What others are seeing from their leaders is usually being copied or followed by them. A leader must be a model or a picture to which people could follow

for the betterment of the whole organization; (14) THE LAW OF BUY-IN. People buy into the leader, then the vision. People look into the leader first before believing on a leader's vision. Even the cause is good to pursue, there is no assurance that people will follow. People follow who they think is worthy to be followed. Trust is an essential element in this law; (15) THE LAW OF VICTORY. A leader must always find a way for the team to win through challenges and obstacles. A leader must be unwilling to accept defeat and be persistent in pursuing victory for the whole organization. Good leaders take responsibility for the success of the team and do what it takes to lead the way to victory; (16) THE LAW OF THE BIG MO. Momentum is a leader's best friend. It is the deciding factor between winning and losing. When there is no momentum, even the simplest tasks seem impossible to finish. On the other hand, if there is momentum, obstacles and troubles feels liken nothing. Every situation poses a challenge, and it seems that finishing a certain task would take forever, but with the help of momentum, every team member is on adrenaline to finish all the tasks in a very energizing way. Minds think fast, bodies respond extraordinarily, and everyone is full of excitement. Creating momentum requires someone who has vision, can assemble a good team, and motivates others; (17) THE LAW OF PRIORITIES. The heart of the Law of Priorities is when a leader understands that activity is not necessarily about accomplishment. People have the mindset that when they are busy, they naturally believe that they are achieving, but business does not equal productivity. Doing activity does not mean making an accomplishment. Prioritizing is the key. Leaders are required to continually think ahead, to know what is important, and to see how everything relates to the overall vision. The key to leveraging the law of

priorities is called the Pareto Principle or more commonly “the 80/20 principle.” If a person will spend most of his or her time working on the things in the top 20% of importance, it will give 80% of the return of what he or she is looking for. Prioritizing time will always direct is to success; (18) THE LAW OF SACRIFICE. A leader must give up to go up. He or she must be willing to sacrifice to uplift others so that he or she can achieve true success. Every person who has achieved success has made many sacrifices in their loves, and the same thing in leadership. The heart of leadership is putting others ahead, doing the best for the whole team; (19) THE LAW OF TIMING. The timing to lead is as important leadership vision and direction. Any wrong action at the wrong time leads to disaster. Resistance will be the result if there is right action but at the wrong time. Mistake is produced when there is wrong action but at the right time. However, doing the right action coupled with right time means success. Timing is crucial in leadership; (20) THE LAW OF EXPLOSIVE GROWTH. To grow the organization, developing leaders is much more important than focusing much of time on followers. People, who can lead well, if trained, will provide massive positive impact on the totality of the organization. By developing leaders, there would be a multiplying effect to the organization, and this is the key to explosive growth of any organization. Leaders who develop other leaders experience an incredible multiplication effect in their organizations that can be achieved in no other way — not by increasing resources, reducing costs, increasing profit margins, improving systems, implementing quality procedures, or doing anything else; (21) THE LAW OF LEGACY. A leader’s lasting value is measured by succession. A leader must always keep in his or her mind what legacy he or she wants to

leave to the team and the organization. Legacy is the final form of leadership. It is the summary of one's leadership effectiveness. Maxwell concludes that, in leadership, achievement comes when leaders do big things themselves. Success is the empowerment of followers for them to do great things and when leaders develop other leaders, significance will come. Legacy is when these mentored leaders are the ones leading the whole team without the presence of the mentors anymore. The abilities of the leaders will not be based on the institutions they established or the accomplishments they made as a team. People will judge leaders, when they are gone, according to the investment made by the leader to the individual team members, and that is the greatest challenge of pursuing leadership in our lives.¹⁵

Knowledge and Skills

Knowledge is subdivided into two parts, factual knowledge and Experiential Knowledge. Factual knowledge when described in terms of learning a certain language, points to vocabulary. Each meaning of a word pertaining to that language must be learned to enable a person to speak the language. In other setting like a salesperson, he or she must spend time in learning the features of the product he or she is trying to sell. Mobile phone customer service representatives must be knowledgeable regarding the benefits and advantages of their plans and services. Pilots must acquire all necessary information regarding protocols and plane operation. Factual knowledge gives us the ability to be confident in what we are doing. It provides us insights that would help in pursuing

¹⁵ John C. Maxwell, *The 21 Irrefutable Laws of Leadership: Follow Them and People Will Follow You* (Nashville, TN: Thomas Nelson), 11-234.

excellence to whatever field or specialization a certain person is taking. Experiential knowledge pertains to how we think on a certain situation we are currently in. It is a kind of knowledge that links to wisdom where the acquisition is through experiencing the actual situation. Experiential knowledge elevates the perception of a person, some of which are the person's values and self-awareness. Maturity, wisdom, character, faith and spirituality, are some of the aspects of experiential knowledge. They are not easily acquired by learning from others alone, but going through the process of life trials and challenges is the key to gain such knowledge. Skills bring structure to knowledge. Skills allow a person to deviate from the current standard pattern but still achieve a satisfactory result. Skill is not going through an approved pattern; rather it is more on improvising or enhancing a set of pattern for a more satisfactory production. Experiential knowledge often leads us into trial and error, and with that, we acquire a certain skill that we could use for us not to repeat the same trial and error on the same instance. Knowledge and skills go hand in hand for further development of human capacity.¹⁶

Mentoring

(1) Humility. A leader must accept to himself or herself that he or she doesn't have all the answers. He or she must see the need for more training and education as a leader. Leaders have to continuously assess their capabilities and weaknesses. If a leader is having a hard time in recognizing his or her own lacking, it will be difficult for him or her to submit in mentoring. To be improved, the humility of seeing oneself as someone

¹⁶ Marcus Buckingham and Donald O. Clifton, *Now, Discover Your Strengths: How to Develop Your Talents and Those of the People You Manage* (London: Pocket Books, 2005), 41-47.

who needs learning and training is crucial. Pride is often the one hindering a certain leader to grow more or to become a great leader. Being humble is not showing someone is weak but rather there is a room for further development into his or her life. (2) Teachability. Teachability means the willingness to learn. A person who is having a hard time being taught upon would not be considered an asset to any organization. A leader who is learning new things will be limited in teaching his or her followers especially in the long run. There is a saying that said, “If your output is more than your input, then upkeep will be your downfall.” (3) Desire. Having humility and teachability alone does not mean mentorability. Having a strong desire in what a person does will lead him or her into being shaped positively. As Winston Churchill said, “The most important thing about education is appetite.” The mold of life includes appetite, passion and desire. A leader must be always hungry to learn in order for him or her to constant grow and allow himself or herself to be able to teach others as well. If a person is an eager learner, he or she will become a teacher of others. Leaders must tackle life every day with a burning desire and constant passion to learn. Being alert and having desire will create an environment of learning.¹⁷

Spiritual Formation

Human Development encompasses how a person grows and changes as he or she journeys into this lifetime. Certain aspects of life are somewhat difficult to comprehend like a person’s wisdom and maturity. As a person matures more, he or she may see that

¹⁷ Hunter, Ron, and Michael E. Waddell, *Toy Box Leadership: Leadership Lessons from the Toys You Loved as a Child*, Nashville, TN: Thomas Nelson, 2009. 43-45.

wisdom and societal contribution becomes more important than pursuing material things, acquiring power, or being in a position. Wisdom contributes in making good choices, critical thinking, and imagination in improving or changing the traditional way of doing things. Wisdom also enables a person to envision and see in a different perspective for a wider scale of providing alternatives for further improvement. The approach to these topics differs to each individual. The human perception or how we think is greatly affected by these, including negativities like hopelessness, anxieties, and depression. By careful analysis of human development, a terminology of a different approach is presented; it is the process of Spiritual Formation or Development. Spirituality is, most often than not, linked to faith and wholeness. Faith is the love of one's self, towards neighbor, and to God. Trust and loyalty backed up by belief and action are the ingredients of faith. Wholeness boosts a person's heart in terms of commitment and connectedness as he or she tries to discover the truth in relation to his or her environment, society, and God. Wholeness directs people in innovating love and opening up more to the idea of faith including stories, rituals, and symbols, as a way of transformation. Spiritual maturation can be acquired through faith development. Faith development enables an understanding in how a person knows, values, and commits, in a process by which he or she finds meaning to life. It also helps the person into entering relationships in ways that nourish the soul growth through transformation. Certain biblical events during the Old and New Testament times introduced spiritual transformation like the story of Moses killing the Egyptian wherein he escaped from Egypt and was called by God to lead the Hebrews (Exod. 2), the experience of the two disciples in Emmaus (Lk. 24), and Saul's

unexpected experience on his way to Damascus (Acts 9). We can observe on these scenarios that transforming moments occur in unexpected time and place, and this is understood by persons of faith that it is a clear act of God. Spiritual development integrates cognitive, affective and purposive ways of learning, and is nurtured through worship and education. There is a strong link between psychology and theology concerning human existence, thus, such formation and development is crucial in understanding deeper the aspects of morality, personality, and ego in human psychology. Understanding human development through chronological age alone will not be enough hence the study of spiritual development is a potential candidate in dealing with human development.¹⁸

Living in a Christian way is a struggle in pursuing wholeness. Wholeness in terms of vision, experience, relationships, and service are major ingredients in attaining Christian maturation. Being whole doesn't automatically mean that someone is complete. Maturation is a process of finding, expressing, waiting and rediscovering, to live on, and not an instant achievement. God is the epitome of wholeness, and we become whole according to His grace. We begin to experience the process of wholeness as we engage continuously in the presence of God as well as our presence in this world. Jesus Christ, who is the image of God, brings experience into wholeness. The following are meditations we seek and depict the texture of life which is represented in full-orbed Christian living; (1) Self-giving and self-finding; (2) Liberation and celebration; (3) Hurt and hope; (4) Strength and vulnerability; (5) Penance and pardon; (6) Love and justice;

¹⁸ Melvin Kimble, Susan H. McFadden, and James E. Birren, *Aging, Spirituality, and Religion: A Handbook* (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2007), 74-79.

(7) Commitment and openness; (8) Justification and sanctification; (9) Speaking and listening; (10) Meditation and contemplation; (11) Excellence and humility; (12) Boredom and beatitude; (13) Death and Resurrection.¹⁹

Biblio-Theological Reflection

Leadership is a common element in an organization or an institution. It is also an important aspect of one's self to be an effective individual in his or her daily life. In the bible, there are many prominent leadership stories like Moses and David. With all those leadership stories, I considered Jesus as the finest example as a follower, a leader, and ultimately as a mentor.

Humility as the Foundation of Leadership

In Philippians chapter 2 verses 5 to 8, we can read Paul's testimony about Jesus who, even though He was in the form of God did not regard equality with God, but He emptied Himself taken the form of a slave and becoming a human which He humbled Himself and became obedient to the point of death. Jesus Christ clearly understands what humility means and its effect to the salvation process of mankind. Jesus was ready to strip out His nature as God and living a human like us, experiencing the same weakness and limitations. Such act would be deemed impossible to us, for Jesus was already in the position of being the highest, which is in the nature of God. But because of God's love

¹⁹ Langford, Thomas A., *Christian Wholeness*, Nashville: Upper Room, 1978. 7-10.

and grace to His creation, Jesus Christ did the most difficult task of being a leader that is to put yourself lower to the people whose duty is to serve and worship you.

For someone to be in the right direction in leadership, humility must be present in that person. In our generation today especially those leaders who have the highest position in any organization, may have the difficulty of serving his or her followers. What Jesus did was the total opposite of our world's acts of leadership. A Senator or Congressman cannot realistically go to a poor family and cook for them nor be in the street and substitute for a street sweeper and be the one to clean the streets. A Bishop cannot literally clean the whole headquarters if ever the assigned cleaners were absent. Position is the mindset of most people today when we talk about leadership. A person, even though he or she is qualified as a leader, but not in a position cannot possibly do much compared to a person who holds a high office. This is the primary difference of what Jesus did. By removing His nature as God, and serving even the lowest class of the society, and being killed without doing wrong, is the perfect example of humility that an aspiring leader should imitate. In John 13:1-17, Jesus washed the feet of His disciples showing extreme humility that is not acceptable to His disciple Peter because Peter knew that it is not proper for a Rabbi to do such an act. Jesus act was to show equality with one another that no one should think highly of himself but rather a willingness to serve. Jesus was not even particular of His nature as God, instead He chose to be born in a poor family, in a manger that is reserved only for animals. Jesus Christ through His humility, made a change in the spiritual arena that would affect mankind's salvation and restoration. Humility makes us a vessel of continuous learning, education, growth, and

development in all aspects of humanity, including physical and spiritual, and that every person should practice living it.

Leadership in Action

When Jesus was 12 years old (Luke 2:41-52), there was an instance where He stayed at the temple after being found by His parents on the third day of their search. Jesus was having interaction by listening and asking questions with the teachers in the temple. People were amazed on how Jesus interacted them through His understanding and the way He answers them. Jesus spent time in understanding the belief of the people. He listened actively and asked questions as well which is very similar to counseling, where someone listens attentively and clarifies the story by asking questions. Leaders need to listen actively to his or her fellow members. As John Maxwell said, “Leadership is influence”, a leader must be willing to spend time with others so that he or she may build up positive influence, deeper relationship and of course to understand them better. Working with your followers with a good relationship standing makes the whole team very effective, ideas would flow naturally, and everybody is willing to take up the whole team to a higher level.

The ministry of Jesus started around the age of 30, where He did amazing things reaching the major cities and towns of Israel. At first, Jesus gathered His 12 disciples and started visiting towns to proclaim the good news and performing miracles. Jesus was acting like a model to be followed by His disciples. He showed them how to minister to people, engage with them, interact with them, and even the handling of encountering

demonic activities. Leaders' duty is to show his or her fellow members how to do a certain task. He or she must be the first to engage and demonstrate the proper way of doing a task. A leader must always stay at the front of the battlefield, showing courage, honor, dignity, and integrity in what he or she does.

From what I have experienced as UMYF, the topmost leaders are the ones dictating his or her fellow members and expecting that member to follow without questions asked. The leaders are spending most of their times thinking and analyzing on what should be the necessary programs for the whole church, but they are forgetting the most important task, that is to be a model and show his or her members how to do and finish a task. In the long run, the members just rely to the topmost leader and feel empty when their leader becomes inactive. That kind of action is not leadership but rather boss-ship. A boss dictates everything regardless of whether or not it is the right thing to do. A boss relies on his or her own capacity to run an organization while a leader relies on the capacity of the whole team, helping them to think and initiate.

Mentoring as the Product of Leadership

Leadership does not end by simply retiring from any position or organization. Leadership must have continuity to preserve the smooth flow of the organization. Mentoring is the final product of leadership. Every leader should have a plan on how to effectively mentor his or her member along the way to ensure that leadership is not broken when transition comes. Jesus mentored His disciples while He was still ministering. In Luke 9:1-6, Jesus gave a task to the twelve disciples to preach, drive out

demons, cure diseases and heal the sick. This particular training is part of mentoring, where the leader let his or her followers experience what the leader had experienced. Mentoring then is not just based on lecture alone but also education in action. In doing so, the mentees are absorbing much knowledge from experience and applying what they are learning on their own way and style.

In Matthew 28:19-21, Jesus Christ gave the final task to the disciples, that is, to go into the nations baptizing them and teaching them to obey everything Jesus had commanded. At this very moment, the disciples became apostles for they are now in a mission to do to the same as what their teacher had done before. There is a leadership transition happened, from Jesus to His disciples, now apostles. As we can observed, for more than 2000 years, the leadership of Jesus Christ and His mission towards humanity is still alive and very much active in major countries worldwide, and mentoring played a vital role in continuing what Christ had started.

In today's reality, mentoring is not given much attention even though that the term exists in every organization especially in the Book of Discipline. Mentoring is all about dictating what a mentee should do and to follow blindly. Many organization and institution are having difficulty when there is a leadership transition. Instead of continuing what the past leader had started, everything is started into scratch. New leader means new policies, new management, etc. One of the primary reasons is that leaders who are insecure do not mentor his or her members. He or she had a mindset that if he or she mentored someone, that someone might become better than the mentor which is of course the target of mentoring – to help someone get better even to the point of being

better than the mentor. Insecure leaders are seen through their way of thinking toward their members, output of the whole team, relationship toward teammates, and the influence the leader has toward his or her organization.

Conclusion

The leadership of Jesus is indeed perfect in every aspect, from humility to His leadership action, and to His mentoring style. Jesus Christ should be imitated by everyone especially those who are aspiring to become leaders or to improve more in leadership. It is difficult for someone to engage in leadership when that person do not have the trait of humility. Just like any other course, leadership also needs education and not just through experience alone. The humility and desire to learn from others will open up the path into right molding of leadership. There is also a time where someone must do his or her own responsibility as a leader, where he or she will engage in situations where leadership is needed. In this manner, the person would gain necessary leadership education that is only possible through experience alone. By amassing great knowledge and experience, the leader must be able to teach others what he or she knows about leadership. This is to have a smooth leadership transition and to help the whole team level up which will give a great positive impact to the organization or institution. Mentoring is the key to a continuous growth, and must be done by all leaders for the benefit of the whole organization even for the longer run.

Justification of the Study

The researcher, from his experiences as a youth leader, has observed that whenever there is a leadership transition in the UMYF Organization of Northeast Pangasinan District (NEPD), the strategies and procedure of each activity is also changing. Some leaders go back to the way where it was already proven that such strategy will not be effective. The researcher concluded then that such kind of leadership transition will not encourage growth to the district UMYF and may become a factor for worsening ministries of UMYF. Other factors is that many aspiring leaders are not confident about themselves, and instead of stepping up, they escape the responsibility and not attend ministries anymore. Also, many elected officers today have insufficient knowledge regarding leadership, they just rely to a single person, usually the president, in every task and just waiting for the instruction of their leader. If their leader or the president became inactive due to various reasons, the whole district officers and its activities are crippled. These situations have a chain effect especially to the future of the UMYF, where the worst case scenario is the diminishing effect of UMYF members engaging in district activities. In this manner, the researcher focused on the study of Leadership Mentoring that would supposedly provide a solution to the problem of leadership transition.

The Leadership Mentoring Program will tackle the basic elements of leadership enough to help a certain organization to grow and develop more. Leadership abilities, Personality Development, Communication Skills, Organizational and Management Skills, and Spiritual Formation, are the main focus of the study to further improve the individual

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so that he or she can have the right confidence, technical and people knowledge, positive influence through communication, and faith and spirituality that would serve as his or her guidance in moral judgment.

CHAPTER 3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the research method, area of study, population, sampling procedure, instrument for data collection, validation of the questionnaire, application of the instrument, and method of data analysis.

Research Method

This research material utilized the descriptive method in assessing the leadership needs of the respondents through the collection of statistical data gathered using a questionnaire as a basis for the leadership mentoring program. As defined by Cabrera and De Asis (2009), descriptive research describes, present conditions, events or systems based on impressions or reactions of respondents. It is the study that can obtain facts about existing conditions or determines significant relationship between current phenomena. It is the description and interpretation of conditions which are prevailing or not, the existence and nonexistence of relationships, prevalence and non-prevalence of practices, perceptions that are withheld, ongoing processes, effects being felt or developing trends.

Research Locale

The research assessed the leadership needs of the United Methodist Youth Fellowship in Northeast Pangasinan District both in district and local church level located

in the eastern part of Pangasinan, Region I Philippines. The respondents were from the following churches:

Figure 2. Map of Pangasinan Province, Region I, Philippines

1. Alibeng UMC - Brgy. Alibeng Sison
2. Amamperez UMC – Brgy. Amamperez, Villasis
3. Asingan UMC - Brgy. Poblacion Asingan
4. Balacag UMC – Brgy. Balacag, Pozorrubio
5. Bantog UMC - Brgy. Ariston West Bantog Asingan
6. Binalonan UMC – Brgy. Poblacion, Binalonan
7. Bobon UMC - Sitio Bobon, Brgy. San Roque, San Manuel

8. Bomboaya UMC - Bomboaya San Bonifacio San Manuel
9. Departe UMC – Sitio Departe, Brgy. Bantog, Asingan
10. Labayug UMC – Brgy. Labayug, Sison
11. Laoac UMC – Provincial Road, Laoac
12. Pasileng UMC – Brgy. Pasileng Norte, Binalonan
13. Pinmilapil UMC – Brgy. Pinmilapil, Sison
14. Pozorrubio UMC – Brgy. Poblacion, Pozorrubio
15. San Roque UMC – Brgy. San Roque, San Manuel
16. San Manuel UMC – Brgy. Poblacion, San Manuel
17. Santa Catalina UMC – Brgy. Sta. Catalina, Binalonan
18. Urdaneta UMC – Brgy. Poblacion, Urdaneta
19. Villasis UMC – Brgy, Poblacion, Villasis

Population and Sampling Procedure

The researcher utilized the purposive sampling in the selection of the respondents. The respondents were composed of NEPD UMYF district and local officers. There were eight (8) positions in local UMYF leadership according to the UMYF Constitution, nineteen (19) local churches in Northeast Pangasinan District, and adding the eight (8) district UMYF position, there were a total population of 160 which was the number of the respondents. In the case wherein the eight (8) positions were not filled up, the following priorities should take place as a respondent: First priority, elected UMYF officers for the

conference year 2018-2019: Second Priority, past UMYF officers within the UMYF age range of 12-23 years old: Third Priority, any UMYF within the local church.

Respondents of the Study

The profile of the respondents corresponded to age, gender, and years of service as UMYF officer in all levels.

Age of the Respondents

In Table 1, it is observed that the age range of 16 to 19 garnered the highest number of respondents (Rank 1) having a figure of 74 out of 160 (46.25%), followed by the age range 12 to 15 (Rank 2, 41 out of 160, 25.63%), age range 20 to 23 (Rank 3, 39 out of 160, 24.38%) and lastly, age range 24 and above (Rank 4, 6 out of 160, 3.75%). The majority of NEPD UMYF are currently in the age range of 16 to 19.

Gender of the Respondents

In Table 1, it is observed that the majority of the respondents are female with 89 out of 160 (Rank 1, 55.62%), followed by the male respondents 71 out of 160 (Rank 2, 44.38%). Among the young people in NEPD, females have the most number, and also dominates the majority of UMYF organizational leadership.

Years of Service

In Table 2, it is observed that according to the total years of service in all levels of NEPD UMYF, the highest is 0.0 to 1.0 year (Rank 1, 47 out of 160, 39.38%), followed by the following in descending order; 1.1 – 2.0 years (Rank 2, 39 out of 160, 24.38%); 5.1+ years (Rank 3, 30 out of 160, 18.75%); 2.1-3.0 years (Rank 4, 23 out of 160,

14.38%); 3.1-4.0 years (Rank 5, 16 out of 160, 10%); and 4.1-5.0 years (Rank 6, 5 out of 160, 3.13%). In this data, the majority of NEPD UMYF are still starting out as leaders of the organization with an experience of 0.0-1.0 and 1.1 – 2.0 years. There is a minimum of 1 year in UMYF local church leadership, while 2 years in district, annual, and national levels according to the UMYFP Constitution. The high percentage of starting leaders indicates a good leadership transition in the district, minimizing the effect of leadership vacuum. Also for UMYF leaders who have an experience of 2.1 up to 4.0 years indicates a smooth leadership transition as they guide those UMYF leadership starters. The figure of UMYF leaders who have an experience of 4.1 and above years are sufficient to guide and mentor their colleagues who are not yet used in UMYF leadership.

Table 2. Respondents of the Study

Age	Frequency	Percentage %	Rank
12-15	41	25.63	2
16-19	74	46.25	1
20-23	39	24.38	3
24 and above	6	3.75	4
Total	160	100	
Gender			
Male	71	44.38	2
Female	89	55.62	1
Total	160	100	
Years of Service			
0.0 - 1.0 Year	47	29.38	1
1.1 - 2.0 Years	39	24.38	2
2.1 - 3.0 Years	23	14.38	4
3.1 - 4.0 Years	16	10	5
4.1 - 5.0 Years	5	3.13	6
5.1 + Years	30	18.75	3
Total	160	100	

Data-Gathering Instrument

The Questionnaire-checklist was the main tool in making an assessment of leadership needs of the NEPD UMYF officers. From the assessment, a leadership mentoring program was designed through a module, and as its final output, a training material was produced.

The questionnaire was finalized through the intensive research of the most common leadership values, traits, skills, and abilities, with the help and advice of the two (2) prominent research professors of the Wesleyan University Philippines – Cabanatuan City.

The questionnaire three (3) sections: I, II, and III.

- Section I covered the profile of the respondent;
- Section II was the checklist for the assessment of leadership needs with 30 items; and
- Section III was an open ended question about the need for leadership skills enhancement and particular leadership skills that the respondent would wish to develop. It had two (2) open ended questions.

The instrument was designed in the modified Likert scale on a 4-point ranking, ranging from “Highly Needed”, through “Needed”, “Little Needed”, to “Not Needed”. The respondents were instructed to respond according to their assessment of leadership needs.

Validity Testing

Validity refers to the capacity of the test instrument if it can or cannot measure what it claims to measure. If the test has a high validity, then the items will be closely linked to the test's intended focus. If a test has a poor validity then it does not measure the related content it ought to. When this is the case, there is no justification for using the test results for their intended purpose. Validity is a degree to which an instrument or test measures what it needs to measure can be classified as content, criterion, logical or construct validity. Similarly Myers (2009) has mentioned that validity of measurement denotes the degree to which the scores from the test or instrument measures what it is supposed to measure. Content Validity is adopted in this research to test the relevancy of the questions in the questionnaires to the research objectives and literature review.

In the validation process of this research, copies were given to the two professors who are expert in research. These professors thoroughly examined the research questions to confirm the appropriateness and relevance of the instrument to the objective of the research. Upon approval, a pilot testing was conducted on the instrument using five (5) random UMYF respondents within the Wesleyan University Philippines, Cabanatuan City. The following objectives are set in the pilot testing:

- The reaction of the respondent;
- Clarity and simplicity of the items in the questionnaire; and
- The needs to include, remove, or change particular items.

After the pilot testing, all items were concluded to be clear and simple enough to understand and answer, hence no suggestions from the respondents are made. The pilot

testing was reported to the adviser, and the adviser suggested adding two (2) open ended questions to finalize the questionnaire.

Data Gathering Procedure

After the validation, pilot testing, and finalizing of the questionnaire, the questionnaires were provided directly to the respondents of the research. One Hundred Sixty (160) copies of the questionnaires were disseminated. The researcher received help from different UMYF local church leaders in disseminating and retrieval of the questionnaires.

Statistical Treatment

The profile and assessment of leadership needs in quantitative data were tabulated categorically, including the answers from the open-ended questions. Percentage, frequency, Weighted Mean, and the ranking system were used to determine the profile of the respondents and in the assessment of the leadership needs. The results were tabulated, computed, and interpreted accordingly.

a. For Percentage

$$\% = \frac{F \times 100\%}{N}$$

Where:

% = Percentage

F = Frequency

N = Total Number of Respondents

100 = Constant

b. For Weighted Mean

$$WM = \frac{TWF}{N}$$

Where:

WM = Weighted Mean

TWF = Total Weight x Frequency

N = Total Number of Respondents

The Four-Weigh Scale was used for the assessment of leadership needs:

$$\text{Range of Scale} = \frac{4 - 1}{4} = 0.75$$

3.26 – 4.00	-	Highly Needed	-	4
2.51 – 3.25	-	Needed	-	3
1.76 – 2.50	-	Little Needed	-	2
1.00 – 1.75	-	Not Needed	-	1

Those items assessed with “Highly Needed” and “Needed” were the basis of leadership mentoring program and module. The rest “Little Needed” and “Not Needed” were not included in the said program and module.

CHAPTER 4

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter presents the analysis, interpretation, and discussion on the data acquired from the respondents in accordance with the problems stated on this study as a basis for the leadership mentoring module.

I. Assessment of Leadership Needs

In this section, the assessment of leadership needs of the respondents are presented. It is divided into five (5) main topics namely, Personality Development, Communication Skills, Leadership Abilities, Other Skills, and Spiritual Formation.

Table 3. Personality Development Needs According To The Respondents

Table 3 showed that Personality Development was needed for a leader which had a weighted mean of 3.16. Positive attitude was highly needed garnering a weighted mean of 3.26 at rank 1. Confidence was needed and had a weighted mean of 3.25 at rank 2. Social manner and behavior which was needed and had a weighted mean of 3.23 at rank 3. Hygiene was needed with a weighted mean of 3.10 at rank 4. Dress code which was needed with a weighted mean of 2.95 at rank 5.

Positive Attitude was given the top priority in terms of personality development due to its verbal interpretation of highly needed, which had a figure above the rest of the items under this category. The data reflected that UMYF leaders should be trained in

accordance to being positive at most. Having a positive attitude enables a UMYF leader be developed in his or her overall personality. The rest of the items had a verbal interpretation of needed which will be included in the leadership mentoring module.

Personality is a pattern of thoughts, feelings, and behaviors that uniquely distinguishes one person from another. It is the combination of all learnt behavior which forms the person's particular responses to environmental and societal factors.²⁰ Personality development is the core of leadership as a preparation for the next-level area of development. It greatly affects the person's capacity to act accordingly in terms of the responsibilities most especially in leading and guiding multiple persons simultaneously. Personality development includes activities for the development of awareness, identity, talents, human potential, human capital, employability, quality of life, and contribution to the realization of dreams and aspirations, engaging in activities that lead people in the role of leaders, guides, teachers, and managers for them to realize their full potential. Personal development in institutions corresponds to the methods, programs, tools, techniques, and assessment systems that support human development individually in an organization. The scope of personality development includes knowing how to dress well, social graces, grooming, speech and interpersonal skills. Personality development also affects the maturity of a person. Maturity is directly proportional to a leader's capability to lead well. Belief, principles, and point of view are often attached to this category. How a person thinks affects the outcome of his or her leadership legacy.

²⁰ M. Gopikrishnan, *A Course in Personality Development*, accessed September 29, 2018, https://www.bharathuniv.ac.in/colleges1/downloads/courseware_ece/notes/BSS201 - PERSONALITY.pdf.

The respondents selected Positive Attitude as being the top priority which verbally interpreted as highly needed. Positive Attitude affects almost everything not just in leadership terms but also as a person holistically. It could be a reason that most of the youth leaders today are in great need of having positive attitude and this need is often neglected. The statement of one of the respondents: *Yes, because other people lack confidence, and positive attitude*, supports the finding. Positivity is observed when a certain problem or issue hinders the ministerial activity of an organization. How a leader acts will tell if he or she is a positive thinker.

Confidence is the capacity to believe in oneself and in relaying his or her thoughts clearly without hesitation in a public setting. For a 0.01 difference compared to Positive Attitude, the respondents seemed to observe that many youth leaders of the district are not confident enough in their way of handling their leadership positions. Confidence is seen whenever there is a need for mass leadership in terms of guidance or in providing information, meetings, conferences, and other situations that requires conveying of thoughts and ideas. Below are some of the statements of the respondents concerning confidence which support the findings:

Yes, because some of the other young people have no self-confidence and they have no fulfillment as a leader/officer/being a young people.

Personality Development and Communication Skills, because how can we lead other youths if we don't have enough confidence or our personality is not well-developed? Enhancing our communication skills is also important in order to influence other people/youth and lead them to Christ.

Confidence, because as a leader, I can't do other things I want to do, so I want to gain more confidence in myself so that I can express my thoughts, and I can deliver them message of God clear and understandable.

Social Manner and Behavior is in tight position compared to the first two with highest weighted mean. It is imperative for a youth leader to be aware of his or her society currently involved with. In this manner, the leader is expected to show proper manner and behavior portraying a biblical model of a leader rooted in humility and servanthood (Phil. 2). Showing of respect is observed through a leader's interaction through manner and behavior. One of the respondents supported the finding, *Social manner & behavior, collaboration and courage. To make the work easier and better.*

Hygiene was selected by the respondents to be on the 4th place. Hygiene is important as it adds to the confidence of a youth leader. Also, hygiene makes someone comfortable for it removes any unpleasant look and smell that would make others avoid the youth leader. It is the scale of how clean, neat, proper, and orderly a youth leaders is. This will attract people by making an impression of being a person who takes good care of his or her physical body.

Dress Code which was the least in this category, is the clothing in the proper setting. Dress code is a sign of how respectable a youth leader is. How he or she dresses can boost confidence. Wearing the proper attire during a conference will enable other people to see the leader as someone who is serious, proper, and confident.

In the leadership training module, the following order was followed accordingly depending on the ranking starting from highest (Rank 1) to lowest (Rank 5) in the

category of Personality Development; (1) Positive Attitude; (2) Confidence; (3) Social Manner and Behavior; (4) Hygiene; and (5) Dress Code.

Table 3. Personality Development Needs According To The Respondents

Personality Development	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Hygiene	3.10	Needed	4
2. Dress Code	2.95	Needed	5
3. Social Manner and Behavior	3.23	Needed	3
4. Confidence	3.25	Needed	2
5. Positive Attitude	3.26	Highly Needed	1
Total weighted mean	3.16	Needed	

Legend:

- Highly Needed - 3.26 - 4.00
- Needed - 2.51 - 3.25
- Little Needed - 1.76 - 2.50
- Not Needed - 1.00 - 1.75

Table 4. Communication Skills Needs According To The Respondents

Table 4 showed that Communication Skills was needed for a leader which had a weighted mean of 3.07. Active listening had the highest weighted mean of 3.18, which had a verbal interpretation of needed. This was followed by the items organization of thoughts and participation during meeting which got the same weighted mean of 3.10, verbally interpreted as needed, both of them having rank 2.5. Then the fluency and proficiency in speaking which was needed having a weighted mean of 3.05 at rank 4. Writing skills which was needed having a figure of 2.90 at rank 5. Some respondents agree to the findings of this category.

Communication skills. It is because if you are good in voicing out your intentions then it will be clear for others, and they will listen as well.

The leadership skills that I wish to develop is the communication, because as a leader, communicating is the most important to show how great a leader you are.

I want to develop my communication with other young people. Because if you always communicate with them, you will know their attitude and for you to help them to be more active.

The communication process in an organization connects all the members of an institution including the external environment. The job of the person with highest position is to securely make a link every resource the institution has, through proper communication. Without the proper element of communication, the capacity to achieve a certain goal in an institution will be next to impossibility most especially if the goal requires teamwork. Communication involves the transfer and exchanging of ideas, information, human emotions, etc. The concept of communication is common understanding between the involved parties, the Sender and Receiver, about what is being communicated called the Message. Message includes ideas, data, statistics, emotions, and feelings.²¹ Communication skills refer to the capacity of an individual in conveying information, thoughts, and feelings may it be in a verbal or nonverbal manner. Proper flow of information through communication minimizes the effect of misunderstanding which results to complications in an organization. This particular skill is a necessity most especially when involved in an organization that aims to be precise, accurate, transparent,

²¹ Sreedhar, C. & Oommen, M. *Training Module On Personality Development*. Accessed September 29, 2018. http://persmin.gov.in/otraining/UNDPPProject/undp_modules/Personality Dev N DLM.pdf.

and informative in all its affairs. Less number of attending delegates in a certain activity or program spearheaded by the district is often a result of lack of information dissemination which includes but not limited to, hard copies of programs, through electronic messages, posters, advertisement, etc. Communication is very much affected by time, so even when the information is complete but is late in terms of distribution, then the information would be less effective most especially when it is done in rush or cram. Communication Skill of a leader is observed when there is an activity being prepared and how he or she responds well in terms of program and information dissemination.

The respondents selected Active Listening as being the top priority in this category. Active Listening is crucial in communication. It is the foundation of conveying a certain information as accurate as possible. Misinformation are often results of not paying attention to the original content or message to be conveyed of.

Organization of Thoughts and Participation During Meeting are tie which means that the two share the same priority. At some point, if there are many information being discussed, it results to confusion and complexity in how to deliver such information. Therefore, the skill in organizing of thoughts will be needed. Organizing of thoughts enables the person to convey the information in order, clarity, and with ease of understanding. Participation in meetings is also needed which means that the participation of a leader's thought would be influential considering that the leader has the bird's eye view in the organization as a whole. This also shows that a leader is attentive,

aware, and understands the current situation of the organization and participates accordingly as a sign of concern to the parties involved.

Fluency and Proficiency ranked 4 in this category as selected by the respondents. It refers to the clarity, clearness, and understandability of the words or statement being spoken of. Also, it affects the meaning and purpose of the whole message. A leader that is fluent and proficient in communicating a certain message is observed when the listeners are not confused and understands well the content of that message, and follows accordingly. One of the respondents agree to this need. *The fluency and proficiency in speaking. Because as a leader, I think it is one of the most important skills a leader must have.*

Writing skills which is the least but verbally interpreted as needed, as selected by the respondents show that, there is a necessity of good writing skills for leaders. Report writing, presentation, resolution, letters, etc. are greatly affected on how a leader will write his or her content. The meaning, order, and clarity of message is incorporated in writing skills. Proper utilization of format and standards will allow the leader's message to be thoroughly understood by the other party. One of the respondents supported this need. *Writing skills, I am not just really good at it.*

In the leadership training module, the following order will be followed accordingly depending on the ranking starting from highest (Rank 1) to lowest (Rank 5) in the category of Communication Skills; (1) Active Listening; (2.5) Organization of Thoughts & Participation During Meeting; (4) Fluency and Proficiency in Speaking; and (5) Writing Skills.

Table 4. Communication Skills Needs According To The Respondents

Communication Skills	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Fluency and Proficiency in Speaking	3.05	Needed	4
2. Writing Skills	2.90	Needed	5
3. Active Listening	3.18	Needed	1
4. Organization of Thoughts	3.10	Needed	2.5
5. Participation During Meeting	3.10	Needed	2.5
Total weighted mean	3.07	Needed	

Legend:

- Highly Needed - 3.26 - 4.00
- Needed - 2.51 - 3.25
- Little Needed - 1.76 - 2.50
- Not Needed - 1.00 - 1.75

Table 5. Leadership Abilities Needs According To The Respondents

In table 5, it can be observed that Leadership Abilities were needed for a leader which had a weighted mean of 3.04. Building relationship had the highest weighted mean of 3.20 with a verbal interpretation of needed, followed by the following items in descending order based on rank; Planning at rank 2 with a weighted mean of 3.09 and verbally interpreted as needed; Collaboration at rank 3 with a weighted mean of 3.01 and verbally interpreted as needed; Execution and Implementation at rank 4 with a weighted mean of 2.99 and verbally interpreted as needed); and Persuasion at rank 5 with a weighted mean of 2.88 and verbally interpreted as needed. All items under this category will be included in the leadership mentoring module. Respondents answered as follows:

Yes, we still need a leadership skills enhancement for us to develop more our skills.

Yes, because as a UMYF officer we need to enhance leadership skill to gain more experience, knowledge, confidence, and other skills that we need to improve.

Yes, it is because leadership must be developed more to be an effective and progressive model for other youth and people around you.

Leadership ability is the lid that determines a person's effectiveness in leadership. If the person's lid or his ability to lead is low, then the potential to lead is also low. When the lid is high, the potential effectiveness of the person is also high. It is the lid towards personal and organizational effectiveness. If there is a strong leadership, then the lid is high. In contrast, if it is not or in a low level, then the organization is limited.²² Leadership ability is most observed in a person's capacity to immediately act, know, and provide solutions to problems or issues that arises which hinders the organization in achieving its goals. In UMYF context, it is usually incorporated on how the program or activity ends up, or how a certain issue was resolved. The awareness of a leader to his or her society, and how capable he or she is in building connections with this society are all part of leadership abilities.

The respondents selected Building Relationship as the top priority in the category of leadership abilities. As John Maxwell said, "Leadership is influence", and for someone to make an influence, relationship is crucial. Building relationship to others means being confident, approachable, and have welcoming gesture so that others will have a comfortable feeling with that someone. Upon building a relationship with others, leading becomes smooth because they see the person not just a leader but also a friend or a

²² Maxwell, John C. *The Complete 101 Collection: What Every Leader Needs to Know; Attitude, Relationships, Equipping, Leadership, Mentoring and Success*. Nashville, TN: Thomas Nelson, 2015.151-162.

family, making requests, advices, or corrections easier to absorb that those leaders without proper relationship.

Planning comes next with a rank of 2. In any organization or even to a personal level, planning is an integral part to enable a person or an organization in achieving its goals and purpose. Planning is the process which makes the general view into a more specific, measurable, attainable, realistic, and time-bound elements. Having a good skill in planning makes a leader direct the whole organization's path properly. One respondent supported the findings. *I think there is a need for leadership skills enhancement especially in planning and execution of plans.*

Collaboration ranked third in this category. Collaboration is the connection, teamwork, and leverage work of the whole organization. A proper collaboration means a good working relationship that would enable the organization to achieve greater goals, and would enable the whole team to level up the whole organization. Collaboration is integral in any organization for this acts as the force that makes the organization move. One of the respondents supported the findings through the statement, *Collaboration, because whenever we hold a meeting to discuss important matters, other members are not present.*

The respondents ranked Execution and Implementation (Output) at number 4. Every plan must be executed and implemented or else nothing will happen even there is much time for planning, and even how specific and realistic these plans are. Among the items in this category, this particular item is end product of the whole process and would require all leadership abilities combined to make the plan successful. A leader cannot

immediately execute a plan for it requires other leadership skills to be developed first to attain a positive outcome. This need was supported by one of the respondents, *Execution and implementation, because in order to be an effective leader, there must be a successful output and not just planning only. For leaders must act.*

Persuasion has the least of the rank as selected by the respondents in terms of leadership needs. Persuasion is the ability to make someone agree to the person's statement. Being persuasive means that a leader is giving enough attention in conveying his or her thoughts as much as possible in order to make his or her listeners agree. By doing this, the leader will be supported by those whom he or she persuaded and can make an impact most especially in decision-making. Persuasion also increases the chance of accepting the leader's suggestions, vision, and goals for the benefit of the whole. The respondent saw the need for this skill, *Persuasion, because I am a type of person who easily gets nervous and my knowledge is not enough to persuade other people. I am also afraid to express my thoughts and feelings.*

In the leadership training module, the following order will be followed accordingly depending on the ranking starting from highest (Rank 1) to lowest (Rank 5) in the category of Leadership Abilities; (1) Building Relationship; (2) Planning; (3) Collaboration; (4) Execution and Implementation; and (5) Persuasion.

Table 5. Leadership Abilities Needs According To The Respondents

Leadership Abilities	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Planning	3.09	Needed	2
2. Collaboration	3.01	Needed	3
3. Building Relationship	3.20	Needed	1
4. Persuasion	2.88	Needed	5
5. Execution and Implementation (Output)	2.99	Needed	4
Total weighted mean	3.04	Needed	

Legend:

- Highly Needed - 3.26 - 4.00
- Needed - 2.51 - 3.25
- Little Needed - 1.76 - 2.50
- Not Needed - 1.00 - 1.75

Table 6. Other Skills Needs According To The Respondents

Table 6 showed that Other Skills were needed for a leader which had a weighted mean of 3.01. Time management had the highest weighted mean of 3.08 at rank 1 with a verbal interpretation of needed. This was followed by knowledge with the organization involved with at rank 2 with a weighted mean of 3.05 and verbally interpreted as needed. Knowledge with the legal aspects and church discipline at rank 3 with a weighted mean of 3.03 and verbally interpreted as needed. Having the same weighted mean of 2.94 at rank at 4.5, the items conflict resolution and financial management. All items in this category will be included in the leadership mentoring module.

Skills bring structure to knowledge. Skills allow a person to deviate from the current standard pattern but still achieve a satisfactory result. Skill is not going through an approved pattern; rather it is more on improvising or enhancing a set of pattern for a

more satisfactory production.²³ Other skills pertain to a set of additional abilities that would help a leader in terms of administration and management of the whole organization.

The respondents selected Time Management as the top most priority in terms of Other Skills. Time management is the utilization of time properly and efficiently to finish all particular set of programs according to the schedule as planned. As part of our culture, there is what we call Filipino Time where the scheduled activity is not followed strictly but is usually extended to the point of having insufficient time to finish everything. Time management is observed when there is a certain program or activity being held. When that program is not in line with the planned schedule, then there is a problem in time management. A properly managed time of execution and implementation will result to a more efficient productivity of the whole organization and may give ample time to other important matters that needs attention. Some respondents supported this need.

The leadership skill I wish to develop is time management, because as a student, it is important to manage your time between the school and the church.

Time management. In my observation, a lot of youth like me are distracted with other things like social media, schools and other activities. So when it comes to church activities, they are always late or absent.

I wish to develop my skills in time management. Because, sometimes I don't know how and what to prioritize.

²³ Marcus Buckingham and Donald O. Clifton, Now, Discover Your Strengths: How to Develop Your Talents and Those of the People You Manage (London: Pocket Books, 2005), 41-47.

Knowledge with the Organization involved with ranked 2 in this category. The UMYF Organization has its own Constitution and By-Laws, also included is the information about the UMYF itself. Having a good knowledge regarding in this matter makes a leader aware of the needs, goals, and mission of the organization that would be reflected whenever an activity or a program is planned. Respondents support the findings of this need. *I want to develop my knowledge with the organization involved for me to have more knowledge about a particular organization, so I can share it to others.*

The particular leadership skill that I want to develop more is the knowledge with the organization involved with, so that I would know all the church activities and solve problems that will be encountered.

Knowledge with the Legal Aspects and Church Discipline ranked third. The UMYF is under the United Methodist Church (UMC) as one of its ministerial arm. The UMC has also its own Discipline that should be followed. It acts as our guiding principles, belief, doctrines, rules and regulations, law and order, etc. It is imperative for a UMYF leader to be aware and equipped with the general knowledge of the Church's discipline. One respondent supported this need, *Knowledge with the legal aspects and church discipline, and time management to do God's work and spread God's word.*

Conflict Resolution and Financial Management got the least rank having the same weighted mean. Conflict Resolution is the person's capability to resolve any uprising conflicts within the organization. Conflict may result to unwanted division, fraction, and may lead to further complications which will affect the organization negatively. A leader trained in conflict resolution will have the necessary tools to minimize the negative effect

of such scenario. Financial management is necessary in an organization. Proper management of finances will minimize displeasing usage of the organization's finances by having such skill, a leader will become aware of the financial status of the organization and act accordingly depending on the situation, and also proper disbursement will be observed. Some respondents supported the findings. *Conflict resolution, because I don't have the guts to tackle conflicts in our home church.*

Conflict resolution. To have a better approach on problem solving.

Conflict resolution, because I don't have the guts to tackle conflicts in our home church.

In the leadership training module, the following order will be followed accordingly depending on the ranking starting from highest (Rank 1) to lowest (Rank 5) in the category of Other Skills; (1) Time Management; (2) Knowledge with the Organization; (3) Knowledge with the Legal Aspects and Church Discipline; and (4.5) Conflict Resolution & Financial Management.

Table 6. Other Skills Needs According To The Respondents

Other Skills	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Financial Management	2.94	Needed	4.5
2. Time Management	3.08	Needed	1
3. Conflict Resolution	2.94	Needed	4.5
4. Knowledge with the Legal Aspects and Church Discipline	3.03	Needed	3
5. Knowledge with the Organization involved with	3.05	Needed	2
Total weighted mean	3.01	Needed	

Legend:

- Highly Needed - 3.26 - 4.00
- Needed - 2.51 - 3.25
- Little Needed - 1.76 - 2.50
- Not Needed - 1.00 - 1.75

Table 7. Spiritual Formation Needs According To The Respondents

In table 7, it can be observed that Spiritual Formation was needed for a leader which had a weighted mean of 3.17. Prayer Life is Highly Needed among leaders and has a weighted mean of 3.31 (Rank 1). Other items are as follows in order of their ranking; Church Ministry Involvement (Rank 2, 3.22, Needed); Truthful / Integrity (Rank 3, 3.15, Needed); Daily Devotion / Bible Reading (Rank 4.5, 3.08, Needed); and Witness, Life as a Model (Rank 4.5, 3.08, Needed). All items in this category will be included in the leadership mentoring module.

Spirituality is, most often than not, linked to faith and wholeness. Faith is the love of one’s self, towards neighbor, and to God. Trust and loyalty backed up by belief and action are the ingredients of faith. Wholeness boosts a person’s heart in terms of

commitment and connectedness as he or she tries to discover the truth in relation to his or her environment, society, and God. Wholeness directs people in innovating love and opening up more to the idea of faith including stories, rituals, and symbols, as a way of transformation. Spiritual maturation can be acquired through faith development. Faith development enables an understanding in how a person knows, values, and commits, in a process by which he or she finds meaning to life.²⁴

Prayer life was selected by the respondents to have the highest priority. Prayer life means the how often a person communicates with God. A Christian leader is selected by God to do His will. To avoid confusion between the will of man and will of God, a leader must always consult with the Lord in everything that he or she does as often as possible. In this way, God's vision, plans, and will are brought to the leader who is eager in consulting God. Prayer life is not limited to leadership responsibilities, but includes every human activity. From being thankful to asking provision, a person should be fervent in communicating with God as much as possible. The respondents seems to observe that leaders of today highly needs to give attention to their prayer life. It is possible that the decision during conferences may not seemed to be of God but of man. Again, consulting with God should always be the first that a Christian person should always do.

Involvement in Church Ministry came rank 2. As stated in UMYF Constitution and By-Laws, a youth running for a position should be actively involved in church ministries. By involving oneself to ministries, the person's faith will develop. There are many important learning while being involved with church ministries that are not learnt

²⁴ Melvin Kimble, Susan H. McFadden, and James E. Birren, *Aging, Spirituality, and Religion: A Handbook* (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2007), 74-79.

elsewhere like service, humility, sacrifice, commitment, responsibility, faith, love, and witnessing. Being active in church ministries means an active lifestyle of the Biblical teachings. As a leader, it is necessary to involve oneself in such ministries so that his or her perspective would widen in terms of handling and serving people, because leadership is about servanthood in biblical sense.

Being Truthful or living a life of integrity has the third rank. Leaders need to be honest in all their dealings because it develops trust and confidence from the whole team. Truthfulness comes when a leader is transparent and is not bound by guilt or shame. Integrity is the person's capacity to walk the talk. When he or she says something, integrity comes if he or she can do what he or she said. Integrity is major component of character because it is rooted in a person's belief and principles in life, and can stand them in times of crisis which makes the person firm in decision making.

Daily Devotion / Bible Reading and Witness (Life as a Model) have the same weighted mean and least on the rank. Devotion is the reflection of oneself through God's word. Faith must be rooted in biblical teaching to be firm. Faith is developed when a person studies the bible and make reflections out of it. It is essential not just for a leader but also for anyone who believes to be soaked in God's words through daily devotion, bible reading and studying. Witness is the person's capacity to reflect his or her faith in daily living, being a role model of faith. Witness also is the way of sharing God's love to others and helping them know Him. As witnesses, we claim to experience God every day, His goodness and grace as we breathe. These experiences are not exclusive to us but we have to make it inclusive, by joyously sharing our experiences with God to others. A

respondent saw the need for this skill. *Daily devotion / Bible reading. I wish to develop this so that we know what God has done because in the Bible, it was all written what God has done to His disciples.*

In the leadership training module, the following order will be followed accordingly depending on the ranking starting from highest (Rank 1) to lowest (Rank 5) in the category of Spiritual Formation; (1) Prayer Life; (2) Involvement in Church Ministry; (3) Truthful / Integrity; and (4.5) Daily Devotion / Bible Reading & Witness.

Table 7. Spiritual Formation Needs According To The Respondents

Spiritual Formation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Prayer Life	3.31	Highly Needed	1
2. Witness (Life as a Model)	3.08	Needed	4.5
3. Church Ministry (Involvement)	3.22	Needed	2
4. Truthful / Integrity	3.15	Needed	3
5. Daily Devotion / Bible Reading	3.08	Needed	4.5
Total weighted mean	3.17	Needed	

Legend:

- Highly Needed - 3.26 - 4.00
- Needed - 2.51 - 3.25
- Little Needed - 1.76 - 2.50
- Not Needed - 1.00 - 1.75

Table 8. Assessment of Leadership Needs

Table 8 shows that all five items in Leadership Needs garnered the same Verbal Interpretation of Needed. The highest in terms of Weighted Mean with a value of 3.17 (Rank 1) is the Spiritual Formation, followed by the following in descending order;

Personality Development (Rank 2, 3.16); Communication Skills (Rank 3, 3.07); Leadership Abilities (Rank 4, 3.04); and Other Skills (Rank 5, 3.01). The overall weighted mean of this category is 3.09 which has a verbal interpretation of Needed. All items in this category will be included in the leadership mentoring module.

Table 8. Assessment Of Leadership Needs

LEADERSHIP NEEDS	WM	VI	Rank
1. Personality Development	3.16	Needed	2
2. Communication Skills	3.07	Needed	3
3. Leadership Abilities	3.04	Needed	4
4. Other Skills	3.01	Needed	5
5. Spiritual Formation	3.17	Needed	1
Total weighted mean	3.09	Needed	

Legend:

Highly Needed - 3.26 - 4.00
 Needed - 2.51 - 3.25
 Little Needed - 1.76 - 2.50
 Not Needed - 1.00 - 1.75

In the leadership training module, the following order was followed accordingly depending on the ranking starting from highest (Rank 1) to lowest (Rank 5) in the category of Leadership Needs; (1) Spiritual Formation; (2) Personality Development; (3) Communication Skills; (4) Leadership Abilities; and (5) Other Skills.

II. Leadership Insights

Question: As a United Methodist Youth Fellowship (UMYF) officer and leader, do you think that there is a need for leadership skills enhancement? Why? And what particular leadership skills do you wish to develop?

All the respondents answered yes that leadership skills enhancement was needed. Figure 3 showed the thematic diagram according to the leadership insights of the respondents. The main themes are as follows together with the sub themes:

1. Communication skills
 - a. Communication Skills (all area)
 - b. Active listening
 - c. Fluency and proficiency in speaking
 - d. Writing skills
2. Leadership abilities
 - a. Leadership Abilities (all area)
 - b. Collaboration
 - c. Execution and implementation
 - d. Persuasion
 - e. Planning
3. Other skills
 - a. Other Skills (all area)
 - b. Conflict resolution
 - c. Knowledge with the legal aspects and church discipline

- d. Knowledge with the organization involved
 - e. People management
 - f. Time management
4. Personality development
- a. Personality development (all area)
 - b. Confidence
 - c. Positive attitude
 - d. Social manner & behavior
5. Spiritual development
- a. Spiritual development (all area)
 - b. Bible reading
 - c. Church ministry
 - d. Daily devotion / Bible reading
 - e. Prayer life
 - f. Witness

It was observed that majority of the answers of the respondents support the findings regarding the leadership skills needs. People management was answered by some respondents as an addition to the skills they want to be developed.

Table 9 showed the multiple responses of the respondents with regard to the particular leadership skills they wished to develop. The category of Leadership Abilities were chosen by the respondents having the highest percentage of skills they wish to develop garnering a figure of 26.23% or 32 out of 122 responses. Figure 6 showed the

percentage amount of each of the leadership abilities needs. Under this category, the following needs were as follows; Leadership Abilities (all area) 12 out of 122 or 9.84%; Collaboration 7 out of 122 or 5.74 %; Execution and implementation 4 out of 122 or 3.28%; Persuasion 7 out of 122 or 5.74%; and Planning 2 out of 122 or 1.64%

The category of communication skills were chosen by the respondents at second place with 22.95% or 28 out of 122 responses. Figure 5 showed the percentage amount of each of the communication skills needs. Under this category, the following needs were as follows; Communication skills (all area) 20 out of 122 or 16.39%; Active listening 2 out of 122 or 1.64%; Fluency and proficiency in speaking 5 out of 122 or 4.10%; and Writing skills 1 out of 122 or 0.82%.

The category of other skills were chosen by the respondents at third place with 18.85% or 23 out of 122 responses. Figure 7 showed the percentage amount of each of the other skills needs. Under this category, the following needs were as follows; other skills (all area) 1 out of 122 or 0.82%; Conflict resolution 3 out of 122 or 2.46%; Knowledge with the legal aspects and church discipline 1 out of 122 or 0.82%; Knowledge with the organization involved 2 out of 122 or 1.64%; People management 1 out of 122 or 0.82%; and Time management 15 out of 122 or 12.30%.

The category of spiritual development were chosen by the respondents at fourth place with 17.21% or 21 out of 122 responses. Figure 9 showed the percentage amount of each of the spiritual development needs. Under this category, the following needs were as follows; spiritual development (all area) 10 out of 122 or 8.20%; Bible reading 1 out of 122 or 0.82%; Church ministry 5 out of 122 or 4.10%; Daily devotion / Bible reading 2

out of 122 or 1.64%; Prayer life 1 out of 122 or 0.82%; and Witness 2 out of 122 or 1.64%.

The category of personality development were chosen by the respondents at fifth place with 14.75% or 18 out of 122 responses. Figure 8 showed the percentage amount of each of the personality development needs. Under this category, the following needs were as follows; personality development (all area) 1 out of 122 or 0.82%; Confidence 14 out of 122 or 11.48%; Positive Attitude 2 out of 122 or 1.64%; and Social manner and behavior 1 out of 122 or 0.82%.

Figure 3. Thematic Diagram

Table 9. Multiple Responses Why There Is A Need For Leadership Skills

Enhancement

Same responses on why there is a need for leadership skills enhancement	Frequency	Percentage, %
1. Communication skills	28	22.95%
a. Communication Skills (all area)	20	16.39
b. Active listening	2	1.64
c. Fluency and proficiency in speaking	5	4.10
d. Writing skills	1	0.82
2. Leadership abilities	32	26.23%
a. Leadership Abilities (all area)	12	9.84
b. Collaboration	7	5.74
c. Execution and implementation	4	3.28
d. Persuasion	7	5.74
e. Planning	2	1.64
3. Other skills	23	18.85%
a. Other Skills (all area)	1	0.82
b. Conflict resolution	3	2.46
c. Knowledge with the legal aspects and church discipline	1	0.82
d. Knowledge with the organization involved	2	1.64
e. People management	1	0.82
f. Time management	15	12.30
4. Personality development	18	14.75%
a. Personality development (all area)	1	0.82
b. Confidence	14	11.48
c. Positive attitude	2	1.64
d. Social manner & behavior	1	0.82
5. Spiritual development	21	17.21%
a. Spiritual development (all area)	10	8.20
b. Bible reading	1	0.82
c. Church ministry	5	4.10
d. Daily devotion / Bible reading	2	1.64
e. Prayer life	1	0.82
f. Witness	2	1.64
Total	122	100.00%

Figure 4. Same Responses On Why There Is A Need For Leadership Skills Enhancement

Figure 5. Communication Skills Needs

Figure 6. Leadership Abilities Needs

Figure 7. Other Skills Needs

Figure 8. Personality Development Needs

Figure 9. Spiritual Development Needs

CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In this chapter, the summary of the result based from the respondent's assessment of leadership needs, conclusion drawn from the analysis of the facts, and recommendation for the further improvement of the whole research, are presented.

The main purpose of the research is to make an assessment based on the leadership needs of the United Methodist Youth Fellowship in Northeast Pangasinan District, and from the assessment, a module will be designed to particularly address the leadership needs of the said respondents. The main instrument used in assessing the leadership needs was the Quantitative-Descriptive method utilizing the questionnaire checklist coupled with open-ended questions. One hundred sixty (160) respondents were involved in this study, 154 within the age range of UMYF (12-23) and 6 who are beyond the age range (24+) but are former UMYF leaders in their local, district, and annual conferences.

Summary of Data

Assessment of Leadership Needs

The result showed that the leadership needs of the United Methodist Youth Fellowship in Northeast Pangasinan District garnered an overall weighted mean of 3.09 which is verbally interpreted as needed. Spiritual Formation ranked first with a weighted

mean of 3.17 and verbally interpreted as needed. The second was the Personality Development having a figure of 3.16 and verbally interpreted as needed. The third was the Communication Skills with a weighted mean of 3.07 and verbally interpreted as needed. The fourth was the Leadership Abilities with a figure of 3.04 and verbally interpreted as needed. The fifth rank was the Other Skills with a weighted mean of 3.01 and verbally interpreted as needed.

I. Personality Development

Positive attitude garnered the highest weighted mean of 3.26, making it rank 1 with a verbal interpretation of highly needed. Confidence followed at rank 2 with a weighted mean of 3.25 and verbally interpreted as needed. Social Manner and Behavior ranked 3rd with a figure of 3.23 and verbally interpreted as needed. Rank 4th was the Hygiene with a weighted mean of 3.10 and verbally interpreted as needed. Dress code, which ranked 5th, had a weighted mean of 2.95 and verbally interpreted as needed.

II. Communication Skills

Active Listening, ranked 1, garnered the highest weighted mean of 3.18 and verbally interpreted as needed. Organization of Thoughts and Participation During Meeting followed at rank 2.5, having the same weighted mean of 3.10 and verbally interpreted as needed. Fluency and Proficiency in Speaking ranked 4th with a weighted mean of 3.05 and verbally interpreted as needed. Writing Skills, which ranked 5th, had a weighted mean of 2.90 and verbally interpreted as needed.

III. Leadership Abilities

Building Relationship, ranked 1, garnered the highest weighted mean of 3.20 and verbally interpreted as needed. Planning followed at rank 2 with a weighted mean of 3.09 and verbally interpreted as needed. Collaboration at rank 3, with a weighted mean of 3.01 and verbally interpreted as needed. Execution and Implementation at rank 4 with a weighted mean of 2.99 and verbally interpreted as needed. Persuasion at rank 5 with a weighted mean of 2.88 and verbally interpreted as needed.

IV. Other Skills

Time Management garnered the highest weighted mean of 3.08 and verbally interpreted as needed, putting it at ranked 1st. Knowledge with the Organization involved with ranked 2nd with a weighted mean of 3.05 and verbally interpreted as needed. Knowledge with the Legal Aspects and Church Discipline ranked 3rd with a figure of 3.03 and verbally interpreted as needed. Conflict Resolution and Financial Management both were in rank 4.5 with the same weighted mean of 2.94 and verbally interpreted as needed.

V. Spiritual Formation

Prayer Life garnered the highest weighted mean of 3.31 making it at rank 1 with a verbal interpretation of highly needed. Church Ministry Involvement rank 2nd with a weighted mean of 3.22 and verbally interpreted as needed. Truthful / Integrity at rank 3 with a figure of 3.15 and verbally interpreted as needed. Daily Devotion & Bible

Reading, and Witness (Life as a Model) both rank at 4.5 with a weighted mean of 3.08 and verbally interpreted as needed.

VI. Leadership Insights

All respondents agreed that there was a need for leadership skills enhancement and development. According to their responses, the themes and subthemes are the following; (1) Communication skills: Communication Skills (all area) with a frequency of 20 at 16.39%, Active listening with a frequency of 2 at 1.64%, Fluency and proficiency in speaking with a frequency of 5 at 4.10%, Writing skills with a frequency of 1 at 0.82%; (2) Leadership abilities: Leadership Abilities (all area) with a frequency of 12 at 9.84%, Collaboration with a frequency of 7 at 5.74%, Execution and implementation with a frequency of 4 at 3.28%, Persuasion with a frequency of 7 at 5.74%, Planning with a frequency of 2 at 1.64%; (3) Other skills: Other Skills (all area) with a frequency of 1 at 0.82%, Conflict resolution with a frequency of 3 at 2.46%, Knowledge with the legal aspects and church discipline with a frequency of 1 at 0.82%, Knowledge with the organization involved with a frequency of 2 at 1.64%, People management with a frequency of 1 at 0.82%, Time management with a frequency of 15 at 12.30%; (4) Personality development: Personality development (all area) with a frequency of 1 at 0.82%, Confidence with a frequency of 14 at 11.48%, Positive attitude with a frequency of 2 at 1.64%, Social manner & behavior with a frequency of 1 at 0.82%; (5) Spiritual development: Spiritual development (all area) with a frequency of 10 at 8.20%, Bible reading with a frequency of 1 at 0.82%, Church ministry with a frequency of 5 at 4.10%,

Daily devotion / Bible reading with a frequency of 2 at 1.64%, Prayer life with a frequency of 1 at 0.82%, Witness with a frequency of 2 at 1.64%.

Conclusion

Based from the results on the leadership needs assessment, it is hereby concluded that in terms of leadership in Northeast Pangasinan District United Methodist Youth Fellowship, there was a need for intensive and intentional mentoring to address the insufficiencies in leadership capabilities and skills of the leaders or officers in terms of spiritual formation, personality development, communication skills, leadership abilities, and other skills.

Recommendation

Through the data as evidence, including the conclusion arose from the study, the following recommendation was proposed:

1. That the designed module by the researcher be adapted by the Northeast Pangasinan District United Methodist Youth Fellowship.
2. That a budget be allocated for the printing of the module to be distributed to the local church.
3. That the designed training module be assessed after a year of its utilization for its improvement in consideration of the context of the mentees.
4. That an intentional mentoring and coaching of young people should be given top priority of the district to make new leaders for our church.

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APPENDICES

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LEADERSHIP MENTORING PROGRAM
UNITED METHODIST YOUTH FELLOWSHIP
NORTHEAST PANGASINAN DISTRICT

Discover and enhance your skills and abilities!

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BY GOD

THROUGH HIS INSTRUMENT

CESAR T. REYES JR.

Leadership Mentoring Program

What is it?

The Leadership Mentoring Program was designed for the United Methodist Youth Fellowship (UMYF) in the Northeast Pangasinan District (NEPD) under the Northwest Philippines Annual Conference (NWPAC) to address the leadership needs of the UMYF based on the research that was conducted by the author as part of his thesis, and to provide a material that would be used for them to mentor others. The intention of the whole program is to train leaders who will become mentors, and these mentors will train young people to mentor as well. Mentoring is a process in which an experienced individual helps another person develop his or her goals and skills through a series of time-limited, confidential, one-on-one conversations and other learning activities. Mentors also draw benefits from the mentoring relationship. As a mentor, he or she will have the opportunity to share his or her wisdom and experiences, evolve his or her own thinking, develop a new relationship, and deepen his or her skills as a mentor.²⁵ Through the program, a youth will be trained in a holistic manner as well, a total character and personal level development. As a person undergoing the program, there will be a massive positive change that will not be limited to handling a church organization alone, but it includes every aspect of his or her society, most especially in both the intra and interpersonal levels. Leadership is not an exclusive club for those who were born with it. Leadership is developed, not discovered. The truly born leader will always emerge; but, to stay on top, natural leadership characteristics must be developed.²⁶ Through mentoring, the growth and development of the NEPD UMYF organization as a whole in the long run can be achieved not only for the benefit of the mentees but including the whole UMC as well.

What's in it?

The module consists of five (5) main topics with five (5) lessons each with a total of twenty five (25) sessions commonly faced by the youth leaders of NEPD. The topics were carefully selected based on the results and data gathered from the perspective of the NEPD UMYF involved in the research program. The following topics are sorted based on the priority level as concluded through intensive research. These topics are as follows:

1. Spiritual Formation;
 - 1) Prayer Life;
 - 2) Church Ministry Involvement;
 - 3) Truthfulness and Integrity;
 - 4) Daily Devotion and Bible Reading;
 - 5) Witness (Life as a Model);
2. Personality Development;
 - 6) Hygiene;

²⁵ Center for Health Leadership & Practice, *Mentoring Guide: A Guide for Mentors* (Oakland, CA: Center for Health Leadership & Practice, Public Health Institute 2003), 1.

²⁶John C. Maxwell, *Ultimate Leadership: Maximize Your Potential and Empower Your Team* (Nashville, TN: Thomas Nelson, 2007), 244-247.

- 7) Dress Code;
- 8) Social Manner and Behavior;
- 9) Confidence;
- 10) Positive Attitude;
3. Communication Skills;
 - 11) Fluency and Proficiency in Speaking;
 - 12) Writing Skills;
 - 13) Active Listening;
 - 14) Organization of Thoughts;
 - 15) Participation During Meeting;
4. Leadership Abilities;
 - 16) Planning;
 - 17) Collaboration;
 - 18) Building Relationship;
 - 19) Persuasion;
 - 20) Execution and Implementation (Output);
5. Other Skills;
 - 21) Financial Management;
 - 22) Time Management;
 - 23) Conflict Resolution;
 - 24) Knowledge with the Legal Aspects and Church Discipline;
 - 25) Knowledge with the Organization involved with.

What's Inside of It?

Each lesson is packed with six (6) different parts in achieving the primary objective per lesson. The mentor and the mentees are free to modify the parts according to their own context, situation, and condition.

1. Insight: A simple insight of each lesson is given to give a minimum idea on what is to be expected. Insights should not be treated as a detailed explanation of the topic and should not be limited to what the insight is talking about. Mentors are encouraged to add their ideas in consideration of the context of the Mentees.
2. Objective: Objective is the goal of the lesson. The mentor's approach should always be in line with the particular objective of a certain lesson. There are three objectives for each lesson that would be achieved through the activities provided, including the outputs and questions for self-reflection.
3. Case Study: Case studies were considered to prepare the mentee's cognitive capabilities through critical thinking. The purpose of the case study is to train the mentee in using critical think in analyzing and in making discernment. Critical thinking process may include the following;
 - a. What is the background of the main character?
 - b. What is the situation and condition of the character?
 - c. What are the issues, problems, or challenges being presented?
 - d. What do you think are the possible consequences of the situation?
 - e. What do you think in the main reason?

- f. How do you plan on approaching the issue?
 - g. What do you think the possible short and long term solutions?
4. Activity: Activities were designed in an interactive way. There are three activities for each lesson based on the objective. The first activity is a way of making the mentees discover, raise awareness, and determine the problems, issues, and challenges on a personal basis. The second activity deals with discussion and lecture from the mentor for added knowledge about the topic and to widen the perspective of the mentees. The third activity is focused on solution-based programs and activities specifically designed by the mentees as a general guide in their own respective organization.
 5. Output: The output aims to continue the learning process of the mentees based on the actual condition and environment. Outputs are the on-field training of the mentees. Outputs are closely monitored and evaluated quarterly by the mentor. This also serves as the goal to be achieved.
 6. Questions for Self-Reflection: Realization, analysis, and reflection based on the adaptability of the mentees on a particular lesson in their daily lives. It prepares them to live out what they have learned by conditioning their mental state according to their own perspective and understanding.

Scheduling

Each module is consists of five lessons to be accomplished in one whole day. All modules shall be completed in 5 days upon strict time management. A sample schedule is shown below.

Day	Time	Module	Lesson
MONDAY *Each Mentee will be tasked to pray before and after the lessons, meal time, and morning and evening prayers.	7:30 – 9:30 AM	SPIRITUAL FORMATION	1) Prayer Life
	10:00-12:00 NN		2) Church Ministry Involvement
	1:30 – 3:30 PM		3) Truthfulness and Integrity
	4:00 – 6:00 PM		4) Daily Devotion and Bible Reading
	7:30 – 9:30 PM		5) Witness (Life as a Model)
TUESDAY *All delegation should be in corporate attire	7:30 – 9:30 AM	PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT	6) Hygiene
	10:00-12:00 NN		7) Dress Code
	1:30 – 3:30 PM		8) Social Manner and Behavior
	4:00 – 6:00 PM		9) Confidence
	7:30 – 9:30 PM		10) Positive Attitude
WEDNESDAY *All delegation should be in corporate attire	7:30 – 9:30 AM	COMMUNICATION SKILLS	11) Fluency and Proficiency in Speaking
	10:00-12:00 NN		12) Writing Skills
	1:30 – 3:30 PM		13) Active Listening

	4:00 – 6:00 PM		14) Organization of Thoughts
	7:30 – 9:30 PM		15) Participation During Meeting
THURSDAY *All delegation should be in corporate attire	7:30 – 9:30 AM	LEADERSHIP ABILITIES	16) Planning
	10:00-12:00 NN		17) Collaboration
	1:30 – 3:30 PM		18) Building Relationship
	4:00 – 6:00 PM		19) Persuasion
	7:30 – 9:30 PM		20) Execution and Implementation (Output)
FRIDAY *All delegation should be in corporate attire	7:30 – 9:30 AM	OTHER SKILLS	21) Financial Management
	10:00-12:00 NN		22) Time Management
	1:30 – 3:30 PM		23) Conflict Resolution
	4:00 – 6:00 PM		24) Knowledge with the Legal Aspects and Church Discipline
	7:30 – 9:30 PM		25) Knowledge with the Organization involved with.

Objective

The Leadership Mentoring Program aims to achieve the following;

1. To provide support to the UMYF organization by empowering and developing its leaders and officers by;
 - a. Training the individual in a holistic approach in terms of character and personality development;
 - b. Train the individual to be equipped and ready in leadership responsibilities;
 - c. Train the individual to be equipped in mentoring and in training other leaders;
 - d. Train the individual to produce leaders and mentors.
2. To continuously support the mentors and the mentees with regular evaluation, consultation, and counseling.
3. To assist the United Methodist Church through leadership, character, and personality development of the UMYF as its ministerial arm.
4. To provide activity output as basis for evaluation quarterly.

Concluding Matters

The Leadership Mentoring Program is designed for group activity. Mentoring is done on a quarterly basis for evaluation and assessment of the outputs. Regular monitoring can be done on a weekly basis for follow-ups, guidance, and for the

improvement of the relationship between the mentor and the mentee. After all the mentees finished the program in 1 year, they will be tasked to mentor 2 young people. The leadership mentoring program will be continuously developed and improved overtime to meet the standard of changing context of the young people. To God be the glory!

MODULE 1 SPIRITUAL FORMATION

Insight

Human Development encompasses how a person grows and changes as he or she journeys into this lifetime. Certain aspects of life are somewhat difficult to comprehend like a person's wisdom and maturity. As a person matures more, he or she may see that wisdom and societal contribution becomes more important than pursuing material things, acquiring power, or being in a position. Wisdom contributes in making good choices, critical thinking, and imagination in improving or changing the traditional way of doing things. Wisdom also enables a person to envision and see in a different perspective for a wider scale of providing alternatives for further improvement. The approach to these topics differs to each individual. The human perception or how we think is greatly affected by these, including negativities like hopelessness, anxieties, and depression. By careful analysis of human development, a terminology of a different approach is presented; it is the process of Spiritual Formation or Development. Spirituality is, most often than not, linked to faith and wholeness. Faith is the love of one's self, towards neighbor, and to God. Trust and loyalty backed up by belief and action are the ingredients of faith. Wholeness boosts a person's heart in terms of commitment and connectedness as he or she tries to discover the truth in relation to his or her environment, society, and God. Wholeness directs people in innovating love and opening up more to the idea of faith including stories, rituals, and symbols, as a way of transformation. Spiritual maturation can be acquired through faith development. Faith development enables an understanding in how a person knows, values, and commits, in a process by which he or she finds meaning to life. It also helps the person into entering relationships in ways that nourish the soul growth through transformation. Certain biblical events during the Old and New Testament times introduced spiritual transformation like the story of Moses killing the Egyptian wherein he escaped from Egypt and was called by God to lead the Hebrews (Exod. 2), the experience of the two disciples in Emmaus (Lk. 24), and Saul's unexpected experience on his way to Damascus (Acts 9). We can observe on these scenarios that transforming moments occur in unexpected time and place, and this is understood by persons of faith that it is a clear act of God. Spiritual development integrates cognitive, affective and purposive ways of learning, and is nurtured through worship and education. There is a strong link between psychology and theology concerning human existence, thus, such formation and development is crucial in understanding deeper the aspects of morality, personality, and ego in human psychology.

Understanding human development through chronological age alone will not be enough hence the study of spiritual development is a potential candidate in dealing with human development.²⁷

Living in a Christian way is a struggle in pursuing wholeness. Wholeness in terms of vision, experience, relationships, and service are major ingredients in attaining Christian maturation. Being whole doesn't automatically mean that someone is complete. Maturation is a process of finding, expressing, waiting and rediscovering, to live on, and not an instant achievement. God is the epitome of wholeness, and we become whole according to His grace. We begin to experience the process of wholeness as we engage continuously in the presence of God as well as our presence in this world. Jesus Christ, who is the image of God, brings experience into wholeness.²⁸

Module Objective:

1. To aid the spiritual development through consistent and continuous prayer life.
2. To be involved in different church ministries.
3. To develop and uphold human truthfulness and integrity as an attitude.
4. To engage in daily devotion and bible reading.
5. To live a life as a Christian witness.

Lesson 1: Prayer Life

Insight

Prayer life means how often a person communicates with God. A Christian leader is selected by God to do His will. To avoid confusion between the will of man and will of God, a leader must always consult with the Lord in everything that he or she does as often as possible. In this way, God's vision, plans, and will are brought to the leader who is eager in consulting God. Prayer life is not limited to leadership responsibilities, but includes every human activity. From being thankful to asking provision, a person should be fervent in communicating with God as much as possible.

Objective:

1. To understand the prayer form of the Lord's Prayer.
2. To guide the learner in constructing prayer.
3. To equip the learner in both private and public praying.

Case Study:

When I was a kid, my mother always taught me to pray to God even though I did not understand what she meant. I grew up attending a Roman Catholic based school in which we always pray at least 3 times in a day. We were taught by that school on what to say in our prayers. The two most common were the Lord's Prayer and Hail Mary. As time goes by, I became used in praying repetitive words over and over again until I

²⁷ Melvin Kimble, Susan H. McFadden, and James E. Birren, *Aging, Spirituality, and Religion: A Handbook* (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2007), 74-79.

²⁸ Langford, Thomas A., *Christian Wholeness*, Nashville: Upper Room, 1978. 7-10.

transferred to another school without religious affiliations. As I attend bible study sessions in the church my mother is bringing me, I learned that prayers have many forms, and prayers should come from the heart denoting that it should not be memorized. I see prayer as a sacred, ceremonial act that must be done wholeheartedly. I grew up with the belief that prayer must be done when asking and giving thanks. The moment I went to college, my prayer changed from formal into more conventional, ordinary approach. I see God as a realistic friend even though I don't see Him. My prayer is talking to Him like a friend, like a physical entity that I could see clearly. The form of my prayer changed because that time I needed someone to talk with regularly, and so I learned that praying in a conversational manner instead of sacred and ceremonial act, would help someone get comfortable in praying to God, like a best friend conversing with you all the time. My name is Hector by the way.

Activity:

1. Each Mentee will write the Lord's Prayer on a sheet of paper and analyze the content of it. The objective is to look for a pattern on how Jesus demonstrated prayer. After doing so, the Mentor will project the Lord's Prayer via Manila paper, Projector, or any other means in order to show to all Mentees the exact wordings of the Prayer. Please note that the version of the Bible must be the same to avoid confusions on words used. Each Mentee will share his or her thoughts regarding the pattern he or she observed and explain the reason.
2. The Mentor will discuss and lecture on prayer, including the different styles and forms practiced by other Christian denomination, early Biblical scenarios, and modern context.
3. Each Mentee will design their own format in both informal (private prayer) and formal (public praying) way including prayer of acceptance in winning souls. Discuss and share with one another.

Output:

1. Design a prayer statement for the following topics: Nation, Church, Family and Relatives, Friends and Enemies, and lastly for their selves.
2. Volunteer to pray publicly. It could be before mealtime, sleeping time, devotional time, etc.
3. Win one (1) soul for Christ through the prayer of acceptance every week.

Questions for Self Realization:

1. How do you define prayer and its importance to faith?
2. What are hindrances you from praying and how do you plan in overcoming them?
3. How will you adapt a daily prayer life?

Lesson 2: Church Ministry Involvement

Insight

As stated in UMYF Constitution and By-Laws, a youth running for a position should be actively involved in church ministries. By involving oneself to ministries, the person's faith will develop. There are many important learning while being involved with church ministries that are not learnt elsewhere like service, humility, sacrifice, commitment, responsibility, faith, love, and witnessing. Being active in church ministries means an active lifestyle of the Biblical teachings. As a leader, it is necessary to involve oneself in such ministries so that his or her perspective would widen in terms of handling and serving people, because leadership is about servanthood in biblical sense.

Objective:

1. To understand the importance of involving oneself to Church ministry in faith and in spiritual formation.
2. To participate in a church ministry.
3. To experience God more through involvement in Church ministries.

Case Study:

Harold grew up as a Methodist for his parents are Methodists since birth. As he became a youth, he was intrigued by the UMYF's activities and wanted to join them so bad. Harold knew little about God that's why he wanted to join the activities because he knows that he will learn more about God. He became an active UMYF since then, participating in different ministries like praise and worship team, choir, Sunday school teacher for children, and he attends district activities like Christmas and Summer institutes. He got bored of the same routine of church ministries and their pastor wasn't involved in youth activities. Therefore, when he entered the senior high school, his time on activities was lessened because of academic works. He slowly stopped from participating in church ministries until the time that he went to college in Manila. Harold lost all his interest in church ministry involvement, to the point of even attending Sunday services. Harold focused so much in his academics and his newfound friends in college.

Activity:

1. Each Mentee will list his or her interests, skills, abilities, and talents, then he or she will analyze on which of these can be applied in his or her respective church. All Mentees will share their thoughts.
2. The Mentor will discuss and lecture about UMC ministries.
3. The Mentees will be grouped into three (3) members and will design a church ministry programs applicable to their respective churches including the execution and program implementation that will provide support to the church's vision and mission statements. Each group will present their programs and have a discussion for improvement and implementation.

Output:

1. Each Mentee will have a church ministry involvement for one (1) straight year in the nearest UMC if the Mentee is away from his or her home church.
2. Finish confirmation class, if not applicable, be a certified lay speaker.
3. Volunteer to be an official delegate in District and Annual Conferences, if not applicable, attend such activities.

Questions for Self Realization:

1. What are your thoughts about church ministry and the importance of involving oneself?
2. What are the possible obstacles for you not to join church ministries or lose your interest and how do you plan on overcoming them?
3. How will you act when your church worker is not encouraging his or her members to be involved in church ministries?

Lesson 3: Truthfulness and Integrity

Insight

Leaders need to be honest in all their dealings because it develops trust and confidence from the whole team. Truthfulness comes when a leader is transparent and is not bound by guilt or shame. Integrity is the person's capacity to walk the talk. When he or she says something, integrity comes if he or she can do what he or she said. Integrity is major component of character because it is rooted in a person's belief and principles in life, and can stand them in times of crisis which makes the person firm in decision making.

Objective:

1. To understand the importance of being true and living a life of integrity.
2. To be comfortable in sharing with others.
3. To be transparent.

Case Study:

Arvie is a youth suffering from depression. Her depression comes in many ways because she doesn't know how to process her feelings. She doesn't open up well even to her best friend about her problems. She became used in handling everything alone. When asked about her life, she doesn't speak up and ignore the question. She doesn't show any transparency in her academics, social life, other involvements, and even about her family.

Activity:

1. Each Mentee will list their fears, worst experiences, situations that brought them trauma, problems, trials, and challenges that is making them weaker. Share and discuss.

2. The Mentor will discuss and lecture about Job's life.
3. Each Mentee will analyze what they have written and shared, then he or she will write his or her coping mechanisms, outlets, or solutions (short and long) in handling each situation. (The Mentor will guide the Mentees by addressing their feelings and letting them think for their own solution, and turning the negative into positive change.)

Output:

1. Each Mentee will open up to God every night everything that happened during the day.
2. Each Mentee will open up to his or her family about his or her current situation.
3. Each Mentee will open up to his or her closest friend about his or her current situation.

Questions for Self Realization:

1. What did you feel as you share your life with your co-Mentees?
2. How do you think that by opening yourself up to others can make you true to yourself and to others?
3. How do you see the relation of by being true to yourself and to others, integrity follows you?

Lesson 4: Daily Devotion and Bible Reading

Insight

Devotion is the reflection of oneself through God's word. Faith must be rooted in biblical teaching to be firm. Faith is developed when a person studies the bible and make reflections out of it. It is essential not just for a leader but also for anyone who believes to be soaked in God's words through daily devotion, bible reading and studying.

Objective:

1. To learn the importance of devotion and bible reading and studying.
2. To make a devotional and Bible study scheduling plan.
3. To produce devotional and Bible study material.

Case Study:

Virgilio just graduated as a UMYF 2 years ago. In his journey as a UMYF, he experienced conducting devotions with his co-UMYF. He struggled so much especially in doing devotions and bible study in a weekly basis, so as time permits it, he does it whenever he feels to do it. When he is burdened with problems and trials in life, he gives more time in devotion because he feels lightened. His devotional and bible study time seems like a situational that he only does it when the need arises in times of trouble.

Activity:

1. Each Mentee will share his or her story about personal devotion and bible study time including the hindrances, difficulties, and confusion encountered along the way.
2. The Mentor will discuss and lecture about different Bible Study strategies, methods, and the process of designing.
3. The Mentees will be grouped into three, and they will design a single bible study lesson. Discuss and share with one another.

Output:

1. Each Mentee will have his or her own timeline per verse/verses for private or group devotion.
2. All Mentees will design at least 5 simple devotional material from their favorite verses.
3. Each Mentee will finish 1 year of devotional material (Daily Bread) regardless of date.

Questions for Self Realization:

1. How do you see the importance of devotion and Bible studying in your faith journey?
2. What do you think will hinder you from doing devotion in a daily basis? How will you overcome these hindrances?
3. What do you think are the benefits when you do devotions in a daily basis?

Lesson 5: Witness (Life as a Model)

Insight

Witness is the person's capacity to reflect his or her faith in daily living, being a role model of faith. Witness also is the way of sharing God's love to others and helping them know Him. As witnesses, we claim to experience God every day, His goodness and grace as we breathe. These experiences are not exclusive to us but we have to make it inclusive, by joyously sharing our experiences with God to others.

Objective:

1. To understand the importance of living a Christ-like life.
2. To realize the Mentee's weaknesses and make improvement.
3. To guide the Mentee in living a Christ-like life.

Case Study:

Benjamin is 15-year-old young people from the province of Isabela. He is always taught to be humble and forgive others. Benjamin is a victim of bullying, after showing patience and ignoring those people bullying him, the situation just got worse. Benjamin became confused of what his parents are teaching him where in fact it is not helping him in his situation. His parents are Sunday School teachers and follow the teachings of

Christ strictly especially humility and servanthood. Benjamin got to the point of disregarding his parent's teachings, rebelled, and follow his own will. He learned how to fight and hurt other innocent people. He became a bully himself.

Activity:

1. Each Mentees will bring out their Bibles and list at least 30 teachings of Christ that a faithful follower should have. Share and discuss some.
2. The Mentor will discuss and lecture the Biblical meaning of Witness.
3. The Mentees will be grouped into 3 members and design a guide in living a Christ-like life based on the lists that they have made. All designs will be presented, discussed, and consolidated to produce a single design that will be posted by each Mentees into their rooms to serve as a reminder of their everyday actions.

Output:

1. Each Mentee will have a poster based on the design made by the whole group.
2. Each Mentee will strictly follow at least 3 Christ-like teachings in a daily basis.
3. Each Mentee will make a weekly reflection about their experiences on how they followed the Christ-like life teachings.

Questions for Self Realization:

1. How do you see yourself living a Christ-like life?
2. How will this lifestyle affect your faith in general?
3. What do you think are the possible obstacles that would hinder you from living a Christ-like life and how do you plan on overcoming them?

MODULE 2
PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT

Insight

Personality is a pattern of thoughts, feelings, and behaviors that uniquely distinguishes one person from another. It is the combination of all learnt behavior which forms the person's particular responses to environmental and societal factors.²⁹ Personality development includes activities for the development of awareness, identity, talents, human potential, human capital, employability, quality of life, and contribution to the realization of dreams and aspirations, engaging in activities that lead people in the role of leaders, guides, teachers, and managers for them to realize their full potential. Personal development in institutions corresponds to the methods, programs, tools, techniques, and assessment systems that support human development individually in an organization. The scope of personality development includes knowing how to dress well,

²⁹ M. GOPIKRISHNAN, *A Course in Personality Development*, accessed September 29, 2018, https://www.bharathuniv.ac.in/colleges1/downloads/courseware_ece/notes/BSS201 - PERSONALITY.pdf.

social graces, grooming, speech and interpersonal skills. Some of the key benefits of developing your personality include the following; (1) Confidence. Through personality development, a person could gain confidence. When you know you are groomed and dressed well, this makes a person less anxious when meeting a person. Knowing the right words to say and how to properly conduct someone's self will increase his or her confidence; (2) Credibility. Personality development makes people more credible. Knowing what to wear and being aware of other aspects of enhancing physical features will add to the person's credibility; (3) Interaction. Personality development encourages people to interact with others. Hygiene and social behavior plays an important role in having a successful interaction toward others; (4) Leading and Motivating. Personality development helps to increase the person's capacity in leading and motivating. A person who has a winning attitude will be better in motivating. People are less likely to get bored, and our ideas will have more impact and credibility. A person can lead better if he or she projects an aura of confidence and credibility; (5) Curiosity. A wrong word if used can ruin relationships. Knowing the right things to say shows both respect and intellectual sophistication because a single wrong word can destroy the conversation's momentum. The best case is when someone is having an interaction with a foreigner. Culture and tradition plays a role in such interaction. Raising the ability of curiosity will avoid complicated communication; (6) Communication skills. Personality development improves communication skills. People are more receptive to what is being said if people are impressed with someone's personality. Verbal communication skills are also part of personality development; improving a person's speech will strengthen the impact of the message. A person cannot win by talent and hard work alone. Personality development is a crucial ingredient that everyone must obtain. Most of the people who are models of great personality have taken a lot of effort in developing their natural features.³⁰

Module Objective:

1. To have a better understanding of one's identity.
2. To grasped the importance of physical and material aspects in projecting oneself toward others.
3. To be aware of the social environment and to respond and adjust accordingly.
4. To boost one's capability of showing himself or herself in a public manner.
5. To build self-confidence in socializing with others.

Lesson 6: Positive Attitude

Insight

Positive Attitude affects almost everything not just in leadership terms but also as a person holistically. It could be a reason that most of the youth leaders today are in greatly need of having a positive attitude and this need is often neglected. Positivity is observed when a certain problem or issue hinders the ministerial activity of an organization. How a leader acts will tell if he or she is a positive thinker.

³⁰ *Ibid*

Objective:

1. To realize the benefit of having a positive attitude.
2. To be able to discern between positive and negative attitudes.
3. To help the Mentee in developing a positive attitude in all situations.

Case Study:

Sixto has diverse leadership experience. Since gradeshool, he is already involved in student government organization until his college. He is well verse in public speaking, at the same time, his socializing skills are above average. As a UMYF, he was elected as president in the local, district, and annual level. When there is a leadership opportunity, he is not afraid to take up the challenge. In his leadership journeys, criticisms, judgments, and unfair treatment were always encountered. He has all the reason to give up yet he finished his leadership position as a UMYF. Most of the time, he thought of resigning and abandoning his leadership responsibilities, but because of his eagerness to prove himself and his capabilities, he went all through the bad experiences and made his way in finishing all the tasks in a rough way. Today, Sixto is already in a leadership management position at his young age of 32 in a company called Gigabyte.

Activity:

1. List 20 situations that you consider as a good thing, and another 20 for the bad things. Share to the whole Mentees what you have written.
2. Pick five (5) of each situation that you think are the most memorable or gave an impact to your life. Make an analysis of each situation on why you consider it either good or bad in past, present, and future impact context of your life.
3. Look for biblical similarities of your situation on both good and bad and make a comparison. Also include the solution and how these stories did conquer the situations.

Output:

1. Make a tarpaulin design about the Spiritual gifts (Galatians 5:22-23) marking them as To-Do Lists, and below are the Not-To-Do Lists found in Galatians 5:19-21. The tarpaulin will be posted inside the room or living room. It will serve as a reminder everyday.
2. Make a daily checklist on about the To-Do Lists and Not-To-Do Lists if something is achieved or not for the whole day. Reflect and make an assessment.
3. Keep in touch with other Mentees through a Facebook group for sharing and helping one another.

Questions for Self Realization:

1. What made you decide that the situations you chose are either good or bad?
2. How will you assess your situations to improve your character and mindset?
3. How do you think that in bad situations, you can grow more? And in good situations you can improve more?

Lesson 7: Confidence

Insight

Confidence is the capacity to believe in oneself and in relaying his or her thoughts clearly without hesitation in a public setting. It is seen whenever there is a need for mass leadership in terms of guidance or in providing information, meetings, conferences, and other situations that requires conveying of thoughts and ideas. Confidence greatly affects one's identity and how he or she projects it. It is the capability of a person to take risks and discern opportunities whatever the outcome is. A person of confidence is not afraid of making changes and moving away from the norm of the society.

Objective:

1. Knowing the Mentee's identity in terms of, but not limited to, character, strengths, and weaknesses.
2. To engage in multiple rejection scenarios.
3. To understand the importance of failures, mistakes, and bad decisions.

Case Study:

Yzel is an 18-year-old girl who is a silent type. She is also an emotional person. Whenever she experiences bad situations that would hurt her, she chose not to speak about it. When asked about personal questions that would open up herself to others, she would rather not speak and ignore the question. One time, she was blamed for making a mess inside their classroom through vandalizing the walls. She doesn't know what to say nor to whom she should tell her side, and the worst was, she got suspended of something she did not do. Because of her silence, people tend to interpret it as a yes or guilty for something.

Activity:

1. Make a SWOT analysis of yourself focusing on character and attitude (who you are – identity) with at least 10 items each that you think are the most significant in your life. Discuss and share with one another.
2. The Mentees will be grouped into three members and they will go out, choosing a person, family, or a house, and they will pray for them. But the goal is to get rejected in 5 different settings as they try to ask for prayer.
3. The Mentor will present 5 different biblical and secular scenarios each of failures and how it became part of their success. The Mentees will analyze

their weakness, mistakes and failures, and will think of how it will help them achieve success.

Output:

1. Every morning and evening, they will affirm their selves with good and positive words through speaking loudly.
2. Experience at least 1 failure per month and make a reflection out of it.
3. Greet every person as much as possible that they will encounter as they go to their destination.

Questions for Self Reflection:

1. How do see that confidence affects your identity?
2. How will you think that confidence is connected to failures and mistakes committed in your life?
3. How will you process your bad situations to grow more in confidence?

Lesson 8: Social Manner and Behavior

Insight

Social Manner and Behavior are integral part of socializing skills. It is true that it might be unpleasant at some time, but by showing the right manners and behavior at a certain time will definitely earn respect from others. These also affects how people will respond to you, in both good or in a bad way. The right manners will gain someone with new acquaintances and friends. Most of the time, it also reduces the consequences of problems incurred because of mistakes. Socializing makes a person grow in all aspects of his or her life. There is a saying that no man is an island, with right manners and behaviors toward a person’s social groups, he or she will definitely have a big circle that may provide help in the future.

Objective:

1. To be aware of social etiquettes.
2. To be able to adjust on different social situations.
3. To learn the benefit of professionalism.

Case Study:

Sharmin just graduated from college at 22. She took up engineering course which is mostly dominated by male. As she was hired for a job, all her superiors are male and in their thirties to fifties. When salary day comes, all her workmates will go out and have fun, relax, and enjoy the company of one another. The usual place is a bar or disco. Sharmin is a religious person and doesn’t drink alcohol. Whenever she is invited to come with her workmates, she just turn them down. During work, all her workmates are working together harmoniously, they are so close with one another that they are not afraid to share their ideas with their bosses. Sharmin’s difficulty started when she couldn’t get along well with her workmates, and she developed some resistance with

them, so whenever she got a constructive criticism, she usually gets uncomfortable. Sharmine, because of uneasiness resigned and look for other job.

Activity:

1. Each Mentee will list atleast 10 things that makes them uncomfortable in a social gathering and find a way to act professionally. Share and discuss with everyone.
2. The Mentor will summarize all the uncomfortable things they have written, then the Mentees will be grouped into three members. The Mentees will act the different uncomfortable way with a scenario of a social gather in 15 minutes. The groups will choose their acting style through draw by lot. After the role play, everyone will discuss and share.
3. Choose a bible setting about social gatherings and discuss how the people acted. Discuss and share.
- 4.

Output:

1. Attend social gatherings and observe how people act like marriage, funeral, birthdays, or places like bar, disco, restaubars, concerts, etc. Try to blend with these people and have at least 3 acquaintances.
2. Go to a place or social gathering you hate the most and learn the culture and etiquette of the people there.
3. List some of your friends' actions toward you that makes you uncomfortable and make an analysis on how you will act in a professional manner with those acts.

Question for Self Realization:

1. How do you understand the word professionalism?
2. What do you think is the best response in situations wherein you feel uncomfortable the most and still showing proper manners and behavior?
3. How will you adjust to the attitude of your social group in promoting right etiquette?

Lesson 9: Hygiene

Insight

Hygiene is important as it adds to the confidence of a person. It makes someone comfortable for it removes any unpleasant look and smell that would make others avoid the person. It is the scale of how clean, neat, proper, and orderly a person is. Good hygiene will attract people by making an impression of being a person who takes good care of his or her physical body. Hygiene also affects the health. Good habits on hygiene lessens the risk of a person getting sick. The inner part of our bodies has its own hygiene, it is usually affected by the food we eat, workout, good sleeping habits, etc. So in summary, good hygiene is the inward and outward body of a person, taking good care of them will result in a healthier and radiant physical appearance.

Objective:

1. To be educated on the importance of hygiene.
2. To create a habit of good hygiene practice.
3. To have a plan on making the inner body clean and good through exercise.

Case Study:

Jojo is at his early forties and currently works as carpenter. Jojo is not used in taking a bath after his work due to personal beliefs. His eating habits is not good as well for he eats meat and drinks carbonated liquid often. People tend to move away from him when he rides a public utility vehicle for his unusual smell. At somepoint, he was diagnosed with dying kidney and liver due to excessive intake of carbonated drinks. The doctor recommended that he go through with dialysis to clean his liver and kidney.

Activity:

1. Each Mentees will share their hygiene habits and how it affected their interaction with other people.
2. The Mentor will lecture on the health benefits of inner and outer body hygiene. There will be an open forum after the lecture.
3. Each Mentee will develop a hygiene habit plan in a daily basis and present it to the group.

Output:

1. Each Mentee will create a schedule for simple exercises, meals, and sleeping hours.
2. Each mentee will have a regular annual dental and medical checkup.
3. Each mentee will have a consistent simple workout program.

Lesson 10: Dress Code

Insight

Dress code is a sign of how respectable a youth leader is. How he or she dresses can boost confidence. Wearing the proper attire during a conference or activity will enable other people to see the leader as someone who is serious, proper, and confident.

Objective:

1. To be aware of the dress code in different scenarios.
2. To develop a habit of dressing in an appropriate manner in all occasions.
3. To be comfortable the proper dress code at all times.

Case Study:

It was during a conference when all the delegates are dressed in a formal attire except for Joseph who entered in a semi casual attire. Everybody looks at him in an

uncomfortable manner. Joseph is conscious of his attire even though he knew that formal attire is the dress code. He did not wear the formal attire because he is not comfortable. He did not socialize with others and sat alone where everybody is having fun and partying.

Activity:

1. Everyone will wear corporate or formal attire during the duration of the event.
2. The Mentees will discuss certain issues that the Mentor will provide in a serious, parliamentary manner.
3. Each Mentee will tell more about themselves in front.

Output:

1. List the upcoming activities that a person would attend and prepare for his or her attire.
2. Attend a mission church then to a big church, and observe the dress code of the congregation.
3. Buy at least 1 set of corporate attire.

Questions for Self Realization:

1. How will you say that proper dress code can boost confidence in your life?
2. What makes you shy on wearing proper dress code and what can you do to solve it?
3. What does the meaning of proper dress code and how would you apply that?

MODULE 3 COMMUNICATION SKILLS

Insight

The communication process in an organization connects all the members of an institution including the external environment. The job of the person with highest position is to securely make a link every resource the institution has, through proper communication. Without the proper element of communication, the capacity to achieve a certain goal in an institution will be next to impossibility most especially if the goal requires teamwork. Communication involves the transfer and exchanging of ideas, information, human emotions, etc. The concept of communication is common understanding between the involved parties, the Sender and Receiver, about what is being communicated called the Message. Message includes ideas, data, statistics, emotions, and feelings.³¹ Communication skills refer to the capacity of an individual in conveying information, thoughts, and feelings may it be in a verbal or nonverbal manner. Proper flow of information through communication minimizes the effect of misunderstanding which results to complications in an organization. This particular skill is a necessity most

³¹ Sreedhar, C. & Oommen, M. *Training Module On Personality Development*. Accessed September 29, 2018. http://persmin.gov.in/otraining/UNDPPProject/undp_modules/Personality Dev N DLM.pdf.

especially when involved in an organization that aims to be precise, accurate, transparent, and informative in all its affairs. Less number of attending delegates in a certain activity or program spearheaded by the district is often a result of lack of information dissemination which includes but not limited to, hard copies of programs, through electronic messages, posters, advertisement, etc. Communication is very much affected by time, so even when the information is complete but is late in terms of distribution, then the information would be less effective most especially when it is done in rush or cram. Communication Skill of a leader is observed when there is an activity being prepared and how he or she responds well in terms of program and information dissemination.

Module Objective:

1. To understand the importance of Active Listening.
2. To train the Mentee in organizing thoughts.
3. To help the Mentee be comfortable during meetings.
4. To help the Mentee in speaking with clarity and sense with fluency and proficiency.
5. To train the Mentee in different writing skills, making letters, and meaningful write-ups.

Lesson 11: Active Listening

Insight

Active Listening is crucial in communication. It is the foundation of conveying a certain information as accurate as possible. Misinformation are often results of not paying attention to the original content or message to be conveyed of. Effective listening and effective speaker are both important to communication process. Communicators must able to express themselves clearly and understand the people they are communicating with. By proper listening, one can encourage other to express true feelings, hopes, aspirations and emotions. Listening to understand is required.³²

Objective:

1. To be educated in the art of active listening.
2. To train the Mentees in active listening through sets of activities.
3. To help the Mentees in processing what they have heard and to respond properly.

Case Study:

Gio is a typical person with who is not fond of socializing with other people. At one time, he was invited by a friend to attend a bible study, and he agreed with a bit of hesitation. He developed a bit of enjoyment as he attend the bible study sessions and after sometime, he actively engaged in the church activities where his friend invited him.

³² *Ibid*

There was an open forum wherein they have to tell their worst experiences that made them give up or their current situation where they are having a hard time coping up. Gio's term to speak came up, and as he speaks, he was always get interrupted by the Mentees through questions, advises, and to relate their story to his story. The whole session took a very long time because of interruptions. Gio lost his interest in finishing and opening up his story and chose to hear others' stories quietly until the activity ended.

Activity:

1. The Mentees will be grouped into five members then they will do a message relay. The message will be given by the mentor. The last person then will be asked certain questions about the message, its meaning, purpose, content, and context. The message relay will not be a memorizing type, but a rather a meaning-expository type.
2. Each Mentees will prepare their selves in opening up his or her life's situations focusing on problems, challenges, trials, and hardships. The listeners are not allowed to interrupt and should focus on the speaker's words and statements. They may use recording devices or write it up in order to understand the speaker's statements. When the speaker is finished, the Mentees will make some confirmations or clarifications and after doing so, they will share to the whole group about their understanding.
3. The Mentees will be grouped into three members, and will make or design their own active listening skills and strategies.

Output:

1. Attend church services and focus on the message of the preacher. Analyze, confirm, and clarify as needed to completely understand the preacher's context, content, and meaning.
2. Listen to one of your friend's story about his or her life, and understand his or her statement.
3. Actively listen to your teacher's teachings in your classroom, and apply the different skills and strategies to help you understand the lessons.

Questions for Self Realization:

1. What do you think is the difference between active listening, passive listening, and listening with the purpose of responding?
2. How do you see the importance of active listening in your daily life?
3. What are your hindrances in doing active listening and how will you overcome them?

Lesson 12: Organization of Thoughts

Insight

At some point, if there are many information being discussed, it results to confusion and complexity in how to deliver such information. Therefore, the skill in

organizing of thoughts will be needed. Organizing of thoughts enables the person to convey the information in order, clarity, and with ease of understanding.

Objective:

1. To educate the Mentees on the importance and impact of properly organizing thoughts.
2. To help the Mentee in organizing his or her thoughts through activities and strategies.
3. To equip the Mentee in different scenarios of organizing his or her thoughts through strategies and techniques.

Case Study:

There is an adult by the name of Daniel who is always chosen by his colleagues to represent their organization in different gatherings worldwide. As an experienced delegate of international affairs, he became popular and gained many acquaintances. Whenever Daniel attended a gathering, he always speak about his experiences and learnings in his organization. He wanted to tell every detail as much as possible. He is not a person having a good memorizing skills, hence, his listeners brand him as a confusing speaker. Because of the many details whenever he speaks up, and if some details are forgotten, he easily jumps on a different topic, and this was his problem. He is having a hard time expressing himself in a complete and detailed manner.

Activity:

1. Each Mentee will summarize their life story in 3 words, and they will share and discuss.
2. The Mentees will be grouped into three members each. The mentor will give them time to read and understand the whole book of 1st Peter, 2nd Peter and 3rd Peter. If there are 4 or more groups, then the mentor can choose any book in the bible with minimal number of chapters. Each group will have to discuss what they have read without re-reading. All they can do is take down some notes in a ¼ sheet of paper.
3. Each Mentee will be given a latest issue found in the news or newspaper, then without re-reading, they will discuss and share about the content, context, and meaning of the article.

Output:

1. Each Mentee will volunteer to become bible study leaders or as preachers, to become their training ground in organizing their thoughts.
2. The Mentees will design a strategy to which they will follow in order to help them organize their thoughts.
3. Attend a meeting or gathering, and apply the organizing of thoughts to express one's opinion.

Questions for Self Realization:

1. What do you think are the advantages of thought organizing in expressing oneself?
2. How will thought organizing help you in your life?
3. What could be the factors that would interrupt you from organizing your thoughts? How will you overcome them?

Lesson 13: Participation During Meeting

Insight

Participation in meetings is needed which means that the participation of a leader's thought would be influential considering that the leader has the bird's eye view in the organization as a whole. This also shows that a leader is attentive, aware, and understands the current situation of the organization and participates accordingly as a sign of concern to the parties involved.

Objective:

1. To help the Mentee to be aware of the necessity of a leader's participation during meeting.
2. To help the Mentee be comfortable in participating during meeting.
3. To equip the Mentee to have clarity, contextual, and meaningful when he or she participates during a meeting.

Case Study:

Walter is a youth leader of their local church in Zamboanga. He always attend higher level meetings like, district, annual, and even national levels. He is always a voting delegate. Due to his shyness, he is afraid to speak up about his thoughts, leaving him uncomfortable after the activity because he wasn't able to share his thoughts and opinions. As much as he wanted to speak up, he feels being shamed without reason. He does not know how to respond properly during meetings and conferences even though he is comfortable with other delegates.

Activity:

1. There will be a role-play and each Mentee will have a draw by lots to know their role to play. There will be no script and should be a free conversation with everyone. The mentor will provide the agenda and the issues at hand.
2. The mentor will distribute a particular issues or problems that the youth is currently facing, and each Mentee will share their thoughts and opinions, together with their short and long term solutions.
3. Each Mentee will select at least three problems or area of development in their corresponding local churches, district, annual, or national conferences, and present his or her thoughts and ideas including short and long-term solutions for each issue.

Output:

1. Every meeting the Mentees are attending, they will actively participate by sharing their thoughts, opinions, solutions, etc.
2. The Mentees will hold a meeting on their corresponding level of focus and they will talk about development of their current organization.
3. All meetings will be properly documented including the plans, approaches to problems, SWOT analysis, solutions, etc. These will be included in the quarterly assessment and evaluation.

Question for Self Realization:

1. What hinders you from actively participating during a meeting? How does it feel when your thoughts are not shared within the group because of these hindrances?
2. How will you make your thoughts be known?
3. How important to you the feedbacks of your colleagues whenever you speak? Are you bothered by these? How will you conquer if you have fear in speaking your thoughts out?

Lesson 14: Fluency and Proficiency in Speaking

Insight

It refers to the clarity, clearness, and understandability of the words or statement being spoken of. Also, it affects the meaning and purpose of the whole message. A leader that is fluent and proficient in communicating a certain message is observed when the listeners are not confused and understands well the content of that message, and follows accordingly.

Objective:

1. To be aware of the language being spoken of including words and terminologies used.
2. To help each Mentee about the importance of simplicity in conveying a verbal message.
3. To help the Mentees to become comfortable during public speaking.

Case Study:

Jen is a youth leader in their district conference for so long. She is a person of commitment and when talking about responsibility, she does it well. For so long, she's not used in communicating in a public manner except for the part of reporting. She always asks other officers to speak to the delegates whenever there is an activity. She told herself that she's not someone fit for public speaking, and chose to work behind doors. She is having a hard time facing the public when there is no notes to read, and she is experiencing mental block.

Activity:

1. Each Mentee share their most memorable experience spoken in different languages. First language is the English, some people may tend to get shy about this but the purpose is for them to communicate not in a perfect grammar English but the content of their experiences. 2nd is through Filipino. 3rd is their native tongue. 4th is the combine language without limits. Each Mentee will prepare 4 different stories of their lives.
2. The mentor will lecture about the public speaking, fluency, and proficiency.
3. Each Mentee will be given bible verses that they would interpret themselves in a public manner.

Output:

1. Every morning, the Mentees will look in their own mirror and practice speaking good things about them.
2. Inside their rooms, they will have a prayer spoken verbally every night.
3. Volunteer as a bible study teacher or Mentor or preacher as a training ground for public speaking and speaking with fluency and proficiency. Ask the listeners for their constructive criticism that will help you improve.

Questions for Self Realization:

1. How will you say that thinking grammar as someone delivers the message affects the way it is being delivered?
2. Do you think that using multiple languages in conveying the message will help in letting your listeners understand more?
3. How important to you are the language barriers and how do you cross these barriers in order to express yourself clearly?

Lesson 15: Writing Skills

Insight

Report writing, presentation, resolution, letters, etc., are greatly affected on how a leader will write his or her content. The meaning, order, and clarity of message is incorporated in writing skills. Proper utilization of format and standards will allow the leader's message to be thoroughly understood by the other party.

Objective:

1. To be educated on different writing formats, skills, and techniques.
2. To guide the Mentees in making a write up.
3. To produce a write up on topics that would be given by the mentor.

Case Study:

Lucille is a well know secretary of their district. Her task is always to write letters for the organization. Whenever she makes a letter, she does it in her own style. She said that as long the message is there, it is enough. One time, she was tasked to write a letter

for a private firm asking for support, but as soon as the manager opened the letter, he immediately throws it out because he saw it as a non-professional and non-formal letter and thought to be a child's play. Lucille was disheartened by the event and vowed not to write any letters anymore. She resigned also as the secretary of the youth in their district.

Activity:

1. The mentor will discuss the styles, format, and techniques used in writing articles, letters, news, stories, etc.
2. Each Mentee will make their own write up based on the discussed styles and format. The mentor will provide the topics to which they'll write.
3. Each Mentee will make a letter addressed to someone. The content of the letter will be provided by the mentor. The letter could be in block style or any other style.

Output:

1. The Mentees will be grouped according to their district level and will write letters for their upcoming activities.
2. The Mentees will write a story about their journey in life.
3. The Mentees will design a standard format in making reports during council meetings and conferences.

Question for Self Realization:

1. How do you see the importance of writing skills? How would it affect your leadership?
2. What hinders you from making a good write up? How will you overcome them?
3. What are your plans in developing more your writing skills?

**MODULE 4
LEADERSHIP ABILITIES**

Insight

Leadership ability is the lid that determines a person's effectiveness in leadership. If the person's lid or his ability to lead is low, then the potential to lead is also low. When the lid is high, the potential effectiveness of the person is also high. It is the lid towards personal and organizational effectiveness. If there is a strong leadership, then the lid is high. In contrast, if it is not or in a low level, then the organization is limited.³³ Leadership ability is most observed in a person's capacity to immediately act, know, and provide solutions to problems or issues that arises which hinders the organization in achieving its goals. In UMYF context, it is usually incorporated on how the program or

³³ Maxwell, John C. *The Complete 101 Collection: What Every Leader Needs to Know; Attitude, Relationships, Equipping, Leadership, Mentoring and Success*. Nashville, TN: Thomas Nelson, 2015.151-162.

activity ends up, or how a certain issue was resolved. The awareness of a leader to his or her society, and how capable he or she is in building connections with this society are all part of leadership abilities.

Module Objective:

1. To train the Mentee in building relationship with other people.
2. To train the Mentee in making and organizing plans.
3. To train the Mentee in collaboration and team work.
4. To train the Mentee in properly executing and implementing the plan.
5. To train the Mentee in persuading his or her team in a proper way.

Lesson 16: Building Relationship

Insight

As John Maxwell said, “Leadership is influence”, and for someone to make an influence, relationship is crucial. Building relationship to others means being confident, approachable, and have welcoming gesture so that others will have a comfortable feeling with that someone. Upon building a relationship with others, leading becomes smooth because they see the person not just a leader but also a friend or a family, making requests, advices, or corrections easier to absorb that those leaders without proper relationship.

Objective:

1. To be able to know the importance of building the right relationship with the whole team.
2. To help the Mentee be comfortable in approaching people and making connections.
3. To help the Mentee in adjusting his or her self in dealing with different kinds of people.

Case Study:

Bok is known to be an introvert person, who is not really into social groups. Bok was elected as a youth leader in their district. Because of Bok’s personality, he is always with his co-officers and seldom meet and greet the delegates in every activity. The delegates develop a degree of fear in approaching him because they knew that they won’t be given attention. There came a point wherein Bok needed some help to finish something, but because he did not have enough relationship with others, and was used in not approaching others, he was deeply troubled in finishing the task alone.

Activity:

1. Each Mentees will be grouped into pair. Each pair will have to know their partner as much as possible, and as deep as possible. To the point of knowing one’s problems and challenges in life, and offering help. The Mentees will share and discuss after the time set by the mentor.

2. The mentor will discuss and lecture about the importance and advantages, including the techniques and skills needed in building relationship with others in the most effective and comfortable way.
3. Each Mentee will go out the venue and look for a stranger that they would talk to. Share the both of their lives, actively listening to the stories of the strangers, make friends with them, and have some connections in other areas.

Output:

1. Each Mentee will know better their closest social groups like church mates, classmates, schoolmates, etc. Establish rapport, offer help to their problems, and make connections with them. Try to be with them for a while to experience their lifestyle and understand their point of view in life.
2. During activities, each Mentees will meet and greet all delegates as much as possible, build rapport and establish relationships with them.
3. Each Mentee will build relationship in a deeper level with their parents, teachers, school administrators, church workers, and higher-level management of their status.

Questions for Self Reflection:

1. How do you see the importance of building relationship with others?
2. What do you think are the possible reasons on why you are having a hard time developing a good relationship with others? How will you overcome these reasons?
3. How would building relationship with others help you in your life as a person?

Lesson 17: Planning

Insight

In any organization or even to a personal level, planning is an integral part to enable a person or an organization in achieving its goals and purpose. Planning is the process which makes the general view into a more specific, measurable, attainable, realistic, and time-bound elements. Having a good skill in planning makes a leader direct the whole organization's path properly.

Objective:

1. To be educated on the importance of planning in all situations.
2. To be trained in the process of proper planning.
3. To produce a planned activity that would be held in their corresponding local, district, annual, or national levels.

Case Study:

Benjamin works as a volunteer in non-government organization. His primary task is to deliver information and maintain the connection of each concerned organization. His

area of focus is the whole region 1. He is not used in plotting or making schedules on when he will distribute programs, he just do it when he feels doing it. One time there was a gathering of different leaders in Region 1 and he was set to distribute the program on that week. He missed that meeting day, and because he needed to relay all the program, he manually went to each municipality and city to give programs, and he finished for almost two weeks including the whole night in travelling. He spent much finances because of travel and for food.

Activity:

1. Each Mentee will write their personal goals, dreams, and desires, including on how they will achieve them in their lifetime. It is the plotting of their lives and the way of making them a reality.
2. The mentor will discuss about the SMART planning and objective, tools, techniques, and other matters that would help the Mentees in making plans.
3. Each Mentee will plan an activity including the financial aspects, resources, materials, etc. in their level of expertise.

Output:

1. Each Mentee will design a plan on their corresponding level of focus on a 1 year basis. If at some point more than two people are in the same level of focus, they will integrate the plans of each other.
2. Each Mentee will plan their lives in a detailed manner including the process of how will they achieve them and it will be posted in their rooms.
3. Each Mentee will volunteer and help in any organization that is tasked to do a program planning.

Questions for Self Realization:

1. What are your thoughts when you try on planning your life and how you will achieve them?
2. How do you see the importance of planning in all situations?
3. How will you react if the plan was not followed and there came an immediate changes on the day of the execution?

Lesson 18: Collaboration

Insight

Collaboration is the connection, teamwork, and leverage work of the whole organization. A proper collaboration means a good working relationship that would enable the organization to achieve greater goals, and would enable the whole team to level up the whole organization. Collaboration is integral in any organization for this acts as the force that makes the organization move.

Objective:

1. To be educated on the aspect of collaboration and teamwork.

2. To experience the advantages of leveraging through teamwork.
3. To enhance the relationship of all Mentees as one team.

Case Study:

Sammy is a one-man team. In everything he does, he's always alone. He graduated from college with a minimal team effort but mostly he was the one who put much effort for the whole team. He believes that if he do it alone, it would be much faster to finish that to be with a team. As he works as an engineer in a well-known electronic company, he was tasked to design a robot that can diffuse a bomb and it was scheduled to be presented next year. Designing a robot means a lot of things like programming, designing of prototype, linkages, movement, precision, balance, etc. Sammy was so pressured that in three months, he only finished the drawing part. He still didn't want to look for a team to finish such project, hence it took him much of his everyday life for one whole year to finish the project. He was successful doing it alone and continues to rely on himself until he got sick and was hospitalized for about a month to completely recover.

Activity:

1. The mentor will facilitate a team building activity that would focus on the mental and physical aptitude of the Mentees.
2. The mentor will lecture and discuss about collaboration, team work, and leveraging.
3. The mentor will facilitate another team building activity with a different groups and members focusing on marketing, cooking, and serving of food for the remaining days of the training.

Output:

1. The Mentees will be grouped according to their cluster, and they will be helping the district officers in organizing, planning, and execution of activities for the whole term of the officers.
2. Each Mentee will volunteer as a helper in his or her church activities and ministries.
3. Each Mentee will volunteer to help in other districts or annual activities.

Question for Self Realization:

1. What are your thoughts about collaboration, teamwork, and leverage? How do you say that being in a team is more advantageous than working alone?
2. What are your hindrances as a person in working as a team?
3. How will you adapt in situations that needs teamwork instead of working alone?

Lesson 19: Execution and Implementation (Output)

Insight

Every plan must be executed and implemented or else nothing will happen even there is much time for planning, and even how specific and realistic these plans are. Among the items in this category, this particular item is end product of the whole process and would require all leadership abilities combined to make the plan successful. A leader cannot immediately execute a plan for it requires other leadership skills to be developed first to attain a positive outcome.

Objective:

1. To enhance the Mentee's capacity to execute planned activities and settings.
2. To understand the different scenarios that may occur during execution and implementation and how to respond accordingly.
3. To educate the Mentees about the importance of execution and implementation, techniques, and skills.

Case Study:

Mark is person who makes plans a lot. He usually communicates with his friends and batch mates about getting together. In planning stage, Mark has endless possibilities for he imagines a lot. Mark has the talent to plot a detailed schedule and timeline guiding him on what to do. When the day is approaching, he changes plan immediately to the point of the original plan is not followed anymore. He keeps on changing plans for he strives for perfection. His friends call him a person of drawing. Because all his plans are for your eyes only and not really happening.

Activity:

1. Each Mentee will be given a task of planning and executing the following; Funeral Service, Marriage, Baptism, Birthday Thanksgiving, and Holy Eucharist. All the details and the know-how will be decided by the Mentees which are grouped accordingly.
2. Making a Habit: Each Mentee will plan a new habit that he or she will adapt.
3. Each Mentee will make a covenant on finishing at least 1 leadership book within a month.

Output:

1. The Mentees will finish 1 leadership or character development book a month.
2. The Mentees will make a new habit or remove old habits that is keeping them from improving.
3. The Mentees will design a timeline in a daily basis for 1 year for their development and improvement as a person.

Questions for Self Realization:

1. What are your thoughts about execution and implementation of plans?

2. What are your usual hindrances that stops your from doing and finishing your plans? How will you overcome them?
3. How do you see the importance of properly executing and implementing plans in your daily life as a person?

Lesson 20: Persuasion

Insight

Persuasion is the ability to make someone agree to the person's statement. Being persuasive means that a leader is giving enough attention in conveying his or her thoughts as much as possible in order to make his or her listeners agree. By doing this, the leader will be supported by those whom he or she persuaded and can make an impact most especially in decision-making. Persuasion also increases the chance of accepting the leader's suggestions, vision, and goals for the benefit of the whole.

Objective:

1. To be educated on the art of persuasion, techniques, and skills.
2. To experience persuading someone.
3. To have the capability of persuading the majority with thoughts and ideas.

Case Study:

Jayson is an intelligent person academically. He was elected as a youth leader in their local church. His members respect his capability to lead and organize the young people. He is always fired up when talking about future plans. Whenever they meet up, Jayson's ideas are not well accepted because it seems impossible for the rest of the young people to achieve. Jayson's somehow lacks detail and is focused on the general viewpoint. Jayson is not eager when it comes on defending his point or giving further discussion. So as a result, the adult members supersede his ideas.

Activity:

1. Each Mentee will be given a topic to which they have to persuade a person outside the group about the information regarding the topic.
2. The mentor will give a lecture and discussion about persuasion, skills, and techniques to further help the Mentees in making their point clear and meaningful.
3. The Mentees will be grouped into three members, and they will be given a theological point to defend and persuade other team based on logic, reasoning, evidences, basis, etc.

Output:

1. Each Mentee will persuade at least 1 stranger in a week that Jesus is the way, the truth, and the life.
2. Each Mentee will propose a program or activity in his or her church and persuade them for support.

3. The whole group will raise P10,000.00 as a support for the ministry program of the UMC through persuading people to offer finances.

Question for Self Realization:

1. How do you see the importance of persuading someone in a proper manner?
2. What are your thoughts about persuasion being used as a tool to garner support from others?
3. What are your hindrances or difficulties in persuading someone and how do you overcome them?

**MODULE 5
OTHER SKILLS**

Insight

Skills bring structure to knowledge. Skills allow a person to deviate from the current standard pattern but still achieve a satisfactory result. Skill is not going through an approved pattern; rather it is more on improvising or enhancing a set of pattern for a more satisfactory production.³⁴ Other skills pertain to a set of additional abilities that would help a leader in terms of administration and management of the whole organization.

Objective:

1. To be knowledgeable in proper management of finances
2. To be trained in time awareness and management
3. To develop skills in conflict resolution
4. To have a basic understanding on the legal aspects and church discipline of the United Methodist Church
5. To gain information about the UMYFP organization and its structure

Lesson 21: Time Management

Insight

Time management is the utilization of time properly and efficiently to finish all particular set of programs according to the schedule as planned. As part of our culture, there is what we call Filipino Time where the scheduled activity is not followed strictly but is usually extended to the point of having insufficient time to finish everything. Time management is observed when there is a certain program or activity being held. When that program is not in line with the planned schedule, then there is a problem in time management. A properly managed time of execution and implementation will result to a

³⁴ Marcus Buckingham and Donald O. Clifton, Now, Discover Your Strengths: How to Develop Your Talents and Those of the People You Manage (London: Pocket Books, 2005), 41-47.

more efficient productivity of the whole organization and may give ample time to other important matters that need attention.

Objective:

1. To understand different culture regarding time.
2. To utilize time efficiently and effectively.
3. To engage in designing a timeline for proper time management.

Case Study:

Elpidio grew up in United States for quite some time. When he turned 31, he decided to stay and continue the business of his family in the Philippines. Whenever Elpidio called for a meeting with the employees of their company, they're usually late by about 30 minutes, including the top executives. It seems that being late on the appointed time is a usual routine for everyone in that company. Elpidio had a hard time considering the fact that the employees are veterans. Instead of forcing his nature of American time, he tried adapting into the Filipino time culture which resulted to time inefficiency and losses in the company.

Activity:

1. Each Mentee will share their thoughts and experiences on how they actually live in a Filipino time culture.
2. The mentor will lecture about different time culture, including the gains and losses with respect to time.
3. The Mentees will be grouped into three members, and they will design a timeline for 1 year in local and district levels UMYF activities.

Output:

1. Each Mentee will adapt an exact time culture for 1 month. It means that in order to achieve it, the time of preparation will be earlier to compensate for the lost time along the process.
2. Each Mentee will design a timeline for themselves for 1 month to be followed as exactly as possible.
3. Make a reflection after the 1-month challenge.

Questions for Self Realization:

1. How do you see Filipino time affecting you and what things are you losing by living under the influence of it?
2. What do you think are the possible solutions to shift your mentality from Filipino time to making it as early as possible?
3. What are your hindrances or obstacles in moving away from the Filipino time concept?

Lesson 22: Knowledge with the Organization Involved With

Insight

The UMYF Organization has its own Constitution and By-Laws, also included is the information about the UMYF itself. Having a good knowledge regarding in this matter makes a leader aware of the needs, goals, and mission of the organization that would be reflected whenever an activity or a program is planned.

Objective”

1. To gain knowledge on the UMYF Constitution and By-Laws of the UMYFP.
2. To be aware on the issues and challenges if the UMYF.
3. To design a program that would cater the issues and challenges as a way of providing short and long-term solutions.

Case Study:

Marita, as early as 14 years old, is already engaged in UMYF leadership. She became the UMYF president of their local church for two years, then another two as vice president of the district level, and finally two years as president of the annual level. Marita is used in socializing with her co-officers, and she is always in their company. Her leadership is focused in planning and implementing activities. She rarely entertain problems and issues of the local churches. As a result, more local churches are unable to attend district and annual activities. Local church UMYF leadership is slowly losing interest due to lack of training and mentorship. Marita finished her UMYF days with gladness, but the problems of the local church UMYF leadership are still present and showing its effects every activity.

Activity:

1. Each Mentee will list at least 10 problems, issues, and challenges that their local, church is experiencing. After doing so, the whole group will connect the problem’s effect to the higher level, on how the problems of the local church will give an impact to the district, annual, and national level of the organization.
2. The mentor will discuss the UMYF constitution and By-Laws with emphasis on position, duties, responsibilities, mission and vision.
3. The Mentees will be grouped into three members. Each group will design a program to address the problems, issues, and challenges of the UMYF with short and long-term solutions.

Output:

1. Each Mentee must have a copy of the UMYF Constitution and By-Laws and he or she is required to read the at least 3 times.
2. Make a SWOT analysis of your present local church UMYF Status.
3. Address the problems based on the designed program made during the activity.

Questions for Self Reflection:

1. How do you see the connection of organization management and problem solving in leadership?
2. What can you say about the importance of giving attention to problems, issues, and challenges, and on how to develop solutions?
3. How do you see yourself as a leader in the UMYF Organization?

Lesson 23: Knowledge with the Legal Aspects and Church Discipline

Insight

The UMYF is under the United Methodist Church (UMC) as one of its ministerial arm. The UMC has also its own Discipline that should be followed. It acts as our guiding principles, belief, doctrines, rules and regulations, law and order, etc. It is imperative for a UMYF leader to be aware and equipped with the general knowledge of the Church's discipline.

Objective:

1. To have an overview on the UMC Book of Discipline focusing on ministerial model, mission and vision, and organizational structure.
2. To become aware on the different agencies and connections of the UMC as a whole.
3. To engage in a deeper level in the ministries of the UMC.

Case Study:

Roger, during the annual conference, was asked by the bishop regarding a certain doctrine of the UMC about supererogation. Roger is being presented as a probationary leading to Eldership. It is customary in annual conferences that a bishop asks a question to a pastor that desires to be promoted. Roger failed to answer the question. The bishop then refereed him back to the Board of the Ordained Ministry for further interview and examination.

Activity:

1. The Mentees will be grouped into three members and will report on topics about the overview of the book of discipline.
2. The mentor will lecture on different agencies, committees, leadership, and connections of the UMC.
3. A global fellow missionary will share his or her story.

Output:

1. Watch the John Wesley Movie entitled, Wesley: A Heart Transformed, or a book about Wesley's life.
2. Involve in ministries that are not currently engaged with.

3. Learn at least 30 hymns.

Questions for Self Reflection:

1. What are your thoughts about the UMC as a whole?
2. How do you see that the UMC helps you in your faith and development as a person?
3. What negative thoughts do you have regarding the UMC and how do you intend to make a change?

Lesson 24: Conflict Resolution

Insight

Conflict Resolution is the person's capability to resolve any uprising conflicts within the organization. Conflict may result to unwanted division, fraction, and may lead to further complications which will affect the organization negatively. A leader trained in conflict resolution will have the necessary tools to minimize the negative effect of such scenario.

Objective:

1. To be educated on handling conflicts.
2. To widen the perspective for a better understand of the situation and be able to develop a fair and acceptable resolution through critical thinking.
3. To design a strategy for handling conflict resolution.

Case Study:

Jen is an elder of a big church somewhere in Metro Manila. AS a pastor and elder, she normally acts in a professional manner towards her members. One time, some members came to her complaining about other church members. Jen had in mind that the people being complained at are the ones closest to her. Because she doesn't want to hurt the feelings of these persons close to her, she just listened to the complaints and ignored them afterwards. She just told them to forgive and forget. After sometime, the complainers left the church for good.

Activity:

1. The Mentees will be grouped into 3 members. Each group will be given 3 issues that is in conflict and they will try to resolve the issues. The issues than can be used can be national issues like terrorist groups, NPA, sovereignty, insurgents, tribal land conflicts, tribal people, and church conflicts that includes the UMYF Organization.
2. The mentor will discuss and lecture on conflict management, resolution, and critical thinking.
3. The Mentees will be grouped into 3 members and will design a conflict resolution model as guide in their own respective organizations.

Output:

1. Each Mentee should resolve all personal conflicts.
2. Volunteer as helper in SPPR committee
3. Review conflicts of the organization or the church and try to propose a resolution.

Questions for Self Reflection:

1. What are your thoughts on conflict resolution and critical thinking?
2. How do you see yourself engaging in conflict resolution?
3. What are your fears, and how will you address that fear in handling conflict resolution?

Lesson 25: Financial Management

Insight

Financial management is necessary in an organization. Proper management of finances will minimize displeasing usage of the organization's finances. By having such skill, a leader will become aware of the financial status of the organization and act accordingly depending on the situation, and also proper disbursement will be observed.

Objective:

1. To be educated in proper financial management.
2. To gain skills and knowledge on financial management.
3. To develop a financial management plan to be used on personal and organization levels.

Case Study:

Fred became a finance officer for 2 years in their district as a UMYF. As a finance officer, he is not into completely detailing the finances and is used by just looking on a bird's eye view of the current finances of the organization. During reporting, he is always asked about the specifics of where and when the finances are being released. He doesn't answer but rather asks his co-officers and they're the ones answering. This kind of scenario continued for two years, and it always ends with confusion and questions.

Activity:

1. Each Mentee will make and present their personal financial report for a month.
2. The mentor will lecture about financial management, including skills and strategies.
3. The Mentees will be grouped into three, then each group will design an activity with financial planning. The activities are district and annual activities like Christmas Institute, CARAVAN, Leadership Summit, in a 5-day program.

Output:

1. The planned financial aspect shall be implemented.
2. Each Mentee will volunteer in committees involved in financial planning.
3. Each Mentee will read the book entitled Rich Dad Poor Dad by Robert Kiyosaki.

Questions for Self Realization:

1. What are your thoughts on proper financial management?
2. How do you see the importance and advantages of financial management?
3. How much is your willingness in adapting proper financial management in your daily life?

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Leadership Mentoring Program for the
 Northeast Pangasinan District
 United Methodist Youth Fellowship

Instruction: Kindly put a check mark on the box for the best description about yourself.

I. Profile

Name: _____ Age: _____

Gender: _____

Total year/s of service as a UMYF officer (Local/District/Annual/National Office):

0.0-1.0 Year: _____

1.1-2.0 Years: _____

2.1-3.0 Years: _____

3.1-4.0 Years: _____

4.1-5.0 Years: _____

5.1+ Years: _____

II. Assessment of Leadership needs.

Legend: Highly Needed - 4
 Needed - 3
 Little Needed - 2
 Not Needed - 1

A. PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT	4	3	2	1
As a youth, I can describe myself in terms of:				
1. Hygiene				
2. Dress Code				
3. Social Manner and Behavior				
4. Confidence				
5. Positive Attitude				
6. Others:				
B. COMMUNICATION SKILLS				
As a youth, I can describe my communication skills in terms of:				

1. Fluency and Proficiency in Speaking				
2. Writing Skills				
3. Active Listening				
4. Organization of Thoughts				
5. Participation During Meeting				
6. Others:				
C. LEADERSHIP ABILITIES				
As a youth, I can describe my leadership abilities in terms of:				
1. Planning				
2. Collaboration				
3. Building Relationship				
4. Persuasion				
5. Execution and Implementation (Output)				
6. Others:				
D. OTHER SKILLS				
As a youth, I can describe my other skills in terms of:				
1. Financial Management				
2. Time Management				
3. Conflict Resolution				
4. Knowledge with the Legal Aspects and Church Discipline				
5. Knowledge with the Organization involved with				
6. Others:				
E. SPIRITUAL FORMATION				
As a youth, I can describe my spiritual formation in terms of:				
1. Prayer Life				
2. Witness (Life as a Model)				
3. Church Ministry (Involvement)				
4. Truthful / Integrity				
5. Daily Devotion / Bible reading				
6. Others:				

III. For the following questions, you may use the back part of this page for your answer if you need additional space.

1.) As a UMYF Officer / Leader, do you think that there is a need for leadership skills enhancement? Why? _____

2.) What particular leadership skills do you wish to develop? (You can list leadership skills that are not listed in this questionnaire) Why? _____

APPENDIX 2: LEADERSHIP INSIGHTS OF THE RESPONDENTS

1. Yes, because skills enhancement for leaders will help them to encourage more youth to be active in their ministry and also to help leaders become more effective, and also for them to find out their own specialties.

Communicating skills and Leadership abilities, because I want to be an effective leader for other youth outside of the church but I lack such skills, and I want them to be developed so that I'll be able to build a campus ministry in our school to win soul for the glory of our Lord and Savior Jesus Christ.

2. Yes, because some of the other young people have no self-confidence and they have no fulfillment as a leader/officer/being a young people.

Communication and Other Skills because I don't know how to express myself to communicate to others and also I have no self-confidence at all in what I am doing. I want to enhance these to show to them what I want to do as a young people.

3. Yes, because leaders are not made, they are molded, so in order to lead other youths, a person should enhance his/her leadership skills.

Personality Development and Communication Skills, because how can we lead other youths if we don't have enough confidence or our personality is not well-developed?

Enhancing our communication skills is also important in order to influence other people/youth and lead them to Christ.

4. Yes, for us to be more productive, effective, knowledgeable, and better leaders through a continuous process of training.
5. Yes, because as a youth, we are in the stage that our faith is still growing. Our skills are still growing. Yet, we need more enhancements on this, to build our own confidence to ourselves.

I wish to develop more in my public speaking skills, and also my self-confidence in front of many people. Though I am not ashamed in spreading the word of God, but more encouragement to improve my self-confidence.

6. Yes, we still need a leadership skills enhancement for us to develop more our skills. I want to develop my knowledge with the organization involved for me to have more knowledge about a particular organization, so I can share it to others.
7. Yes, because as a UMYF officer we need to enhance leadership skill to gain more experience, knowledge, confidence, and other skills that we need to improve.

Confidence, because as a leader, I can't do other things I want to do, so I want to gain more confidence in myself so that I can express my thoughts, and I can deliver them message of God clear and understandable.

8. Yes, as a leader, we needed enhancement so that we will become more skillful, and to know what we are doing.

Daily devotion / Bible reading. I wish to develop this so that we know what God has done because in the Bible, it was all written what God has done to His disciples.

9. Yes, to strengthen our camaraderie as young people.

Daily devotion / Bible reading. I wish to develop this so that we know what God has done.

10. Relationship with others, so that all of us can understand one another, and to have a deeper relationship.

11. Yes, so that you can handle your member and you know how to handle every situation that happens. If you have the skills of a leader, you can easily manage how to become a leader.

Being a leader in ministries like for example in theatrics, I want to develop this skills so that I can be a good leader and I can do better. I can be a better leader for God.

12. Yes, because being a leader is not easy, we need to be equipped to enhance and develop our abilities and skills.

The power of involving people is the skill I want to develop, because it is easier to lead if you are all united

13. Yes, to be effective in ministry, breaking through with the love of Christ, then you, as a church leader, need to be skillfully move in the right direction with the right source of confidence, having the right objectives and the right means of getting there. And must acquire leadership skills such as lining up with God's character and ways to be empowered by the Holy Spirit ad produce eternal results.

Communication, but first I must have intimate relationship with God through prayer, and demonstrating trust and reliance on Him, then with people, demonstrating a desire for unity and participation. Second, listening first to God leading to wisdom

- and understanding, then to people, leading them to greater awareness and accountability.
14. Yes, because being a leader means you have to step out of your boundaries. You have to enhance your skills in order to persuade more people and in order to be a good model to other youth.
- Persuasion. Because I find it hard to persuade people to believe in what I say.
15. Yes, because other people lack confidence, and positive attitude.
- For me the leadership skills that I want to develop is public speaking. I am too shy to speak in front of many people. Sometimes, I stutter and I want to overcome the fear of being in public.
16. Yes, it is because leadership must be developed more to be an effective and progressive model for other youth and people around you.
- Communication skills. It is because if you are good in voicing out your intentions then it will be clear for others, and they will listen as well.
17. Yes, so that our improvement rate will increase through proper leadership skills.
- Collaboration, because whenever we hold a meeting to discuss important matters, other members are not present.
18. Yes, it will be beneficial to us UMYF to enhance our leadership, to improve in all aspects needed to become a vital organization.
- Collaboration, persuasion, and people management.
19. Yes, in order to be a great leader for the improvement of the church.

- Confidence in speaking and to ourselves so that, as officers, we learn how to trust ourselves more.
20. Yes, because as a leader, he/she needs a leadership enhancement so that he/she can handle well their members in church.
- The leadership skills that I wish to develop is the communication, because as a leader, communicating is the most important to show how great a leader you are.
21. Yes, because as a leader, we need to be open for more assistance and enhancement for us to know the things that need improvement.
- I think the particular skills that needs to be developed is the spiritual formation, because as a leader, we need to be always guided and have a personal encounter with God in our daily lives.
22. Yes. As a leader, there is a need for skills enhancement for your co-officers and the youth. Because if you have the skills enhancement, you will now what do to do to encourage others to be more active and plan more activities.
- I want to develop my communication with other young people. Because if you always communicate with them, you will know their attitude and for you to help them to be more active.
23. Yes. Because being a leader, we need to build more our relationship with other youth, and also we need to build more relationship with God.
- For me, I want to develop a particular leadership skill in becoming more active, so that I can encourage more young people to grow more in faith.
24. Yes, because it is essential for leaders to undergo training to become effective.

Leadership training on how to address the attitude of the millennial generation.

25. Yes, because we need to be the one who knows that things we can do for the church or the plan or vision so that we can achieve success by using the skills that we enhance.

I want to learn all leadership skills so that I can grow more.

26. Yes, as a leader, we need to enhance our skills to make our members grow and be motivated to do better because being a leader, we need to know our members and have a good communication with them.

In my opinion, we need the good leading to our members, to make them good, and by doing something as a youth. Second is care. As a leader, we need to show proper care to everyone. Third is commitment. Being a leader means having the commitment in fulfilling God's plan and to be more faithful in Him.

27. Yes, a UMYF leader needs to enhance his/her skills in terms of leadership for he/she acts as a role model to everyone. He/she needs to improve the ability/skill that he/she has in order to have a better result.

Being a good follower and a responsible leader.

28. Yes, because there is a lot of youth officers/leaders who doesn't know the real meaning of leadership.

Understanding, because I observe that there is no permanent youth in church because they don't understand each other and they judge everyone so the other youth backslide.

29. Yes, because most of the leaders lack self-encouragement and our skills in terms of being a leader is not sufficient.

Persuasion, because I am a type of person who easily gets nervous and my knowledge is not enough to persuade other people. I am also afraid to express my thoughts and feelings.

30. Yes, because we know that not all officers/leaders are ready to handle a major problem in the ministries.

Leadership skills that I wish to develop are to be more patient and strong enough to stand as a leader, being firm in regulating words of God, motivate and inspire young people to always have faith in God Almighty.

31. Yes, because it is very important to my life to improve my faith in God.

Time management so that I can avoid being late in church activity and divine service.

32. Yes, because in my observation, we are lacking in knowledge in terms of leading others.

Conflict resolution, because I don't have the guts to tackle conflicts in our home church.

33. As a leader, I think that there is a need for leadership enhancement to improve in managing my time.

The leadership skill I wish to develop is time management, because as a student, it is important to manage your time between the school and the church.

34. We really need this leadership skills enhancement for us to be able to lead properly.

We need this because we need to know the step by step process of leading.

- Skills that tackles lack of interest and time.
35. Yes, because our local church is in need of a responsible leader.
- Time management, to encourage my fellow youth to be on time.
36. Yes, because of lack of self-confidence, and to enhance leadership skills that will lead to a more organized and functional organization.
- I want to develop my communication skills.
37. Yes, for me enhancement of leadership will help the leader to motivate and help also the children/adults to be more active during Sundays and fellowships.
- I want to know everything about leadership.
38. Yes, because as a leader we need to enhance or develop our skills to be a good leader, also a good model to others.
- Encourage the members of UMYF to continue their skills and to improve it.
39. Yes, we need to enhance our leadership skills to become a role model to others.
- We need to develop time management to balance our studies and in being a leader.
40. Yes, for us to earn more knowledge about leadership.
- Time management. In my observation, a lot of youth like me are distracted with other things like social media, schools and other activities. So when it comes to church activities, they are always late or absent.
41. Yes, since people change from time to time, I think that leadership skills enhancement is very much needed to cope up with the needs of the people you are working with as a leader.

- The ability to concretize everything that has planned. Action is always on top of words.
42. Yes, because they needed to improve their leadership skills.
- The ability to manage time and behavior, because that is one of the problems of our church.
43. Yes, we need a leadership skills to improve the young people's skills.
- I wish to develop the time management skills of every young people.
44. Yes, because leadership skill enhancement is one of the process to become an effective leader. It is needed to gain and enhance your knowledge and wisdom for being a leader.
- Speaking, planning, and decision making. I lack in these skills that is why I consider not a fully effective leader.
45. There is a need? Yes! It is needed of every UMYF leader, in order for them to grow, stay focused to God and to the church.
- For me personally, I want to overcome my shyness to speak, especially in public speaking and praying in public, because sometimes, there's a lot of thoughts in my mind nut I cannot express it on by one.
46. Yes, because as a leader, you also need to learn about things.
- I want to develop my skills in speaking and I want to develop also my skills in my ministry and in leading the Bible study or Sunday school.
47. Yes, because a leader also need to learn and enhance their skills as a leader to lead.

I choose to develop the leadership skills because most of the young people, they do not know about leadership.

48. Yes, because a leader should be skillful and knowledgeable in all aspects not just focusing and paying attention on a method. These can help in enriching a church ministry.

The particular leadership skills that I want to develop are competency, character, and ability. These skills can help a leader in building a solid ground in a church ministry.

A leader must be an influencer, motivator, and the one who can be a comfort zone.

49. Yes, for we can improve whatever skills we have in terms of leadership.

I think leadership abilities and spiritual formation are some to be developed as a youth leader and a Christian. And I think that these two are the weaknesses of every youth.

50. Yes, because a leader must have continuous knowledge not just enough knowledge.

Motivation, persuasion, and time management.

51. Yes, to develop my other skills.

I want to develop my skill in teaching children, because I am impatient.

52. Yes, there is a great need for leadership skills enhancement because gaining knowledge and skills from the experts will help you lead and solve problems. Without this, you will easily fall as well as your members.

Writing skills, I am not just really good at it.

53. Yes, to improve character and attitude.

Bible reading to know what to say.

54. Yes, because it is necessary to mold excellence towards our organization.

Faith, because there is a time that I forgot to pray.

55. Yes, because some leaders can't help their fellow members.

Confidence and collaboration. Because I'm shy to share my ideas toward my fellow members sometimes.

56. Yes, because through this enhancement, I could be more responsible in all the things that I while make as a leader.

I wish to develop my skills in time management. Because, sometimes I don't know how and what to prioritize.

57. Yes, because having a leadership skills enhancement helps me to be better. As a UMYF, I need to have skills to make other things easy.

Communication skills, because I'm feeling shy when I communicate to the person who I am not close with. I want to develop this skill to know more other UMYF.

58. Yes, for you to establish more on leadership skills and also to share it with others.

And also to understand what you want to share with others.

The particular leadership skill that I wish to develop is time management, because sometimes, I don't even prioritize the time especially on attending church every Sunday.

59. Yes, because having a leadership skills, it makes us a good leader, good disciples and to be a good model to the youth.

- The leadership skills which I wish to develop is my confidence, commitment, and time management, because I don't have enough confidence to face other people and to speak to them.
60. Yes, because we need to develop how to manage and how to solve problems and how to lead others.
- Knowledge with the legal aspects and church discipline, and time management to do God's work and spread God's word.
61. Yes, to be able to serve and influence others more effectively.
- Confidence, I meant confidence with God because we can't do the things we want to do if we don't have confidence or believe that it is going to work. We have to believe not in ourselves but the God that is working in us.
62. Yes, because what you need is a leadership that will lead.
- The leadership skills that I wish to develop are confidence and positivity, because without these skills, I cannot lead well.
63. Yes, for us to make more disciples and for the continuity of young people's organization in the local churches for the next generation of young people.
- Music ministry, so that in the fishing of men or discipleship, the young people will never get bored.
64. Yes, because being a leader, I have to be skilled and knowledgeable so that I can do all my duties as a leader
- Open mindedness and being a good listener, because I have to listen and understand the needs of all my members so that we can cooperate well.

65. Yes, as a leader there is a need for a leadership enhancement because we need enough skills and knowledge of what organization we have, for us to become effective leaders, we need to enhance and develop our skills.

Spiritual formation, because my spiritual formation skills is not really good. As a leader, this is the most effective skills that we must have.

66. I think there is a need for leadership skills enhancement especially in planning and execution of plans.

I want to enhance my knowledge about the youth, church discipline, and in youth ministries.

67. Yes, because as an officer/leader, I must be a good leader to them. By showing them my skills in doing good and be a good model to all. For them to know what is the best and right thing to do as a member of our ministry and church.

For being active and devoted, because I want to experience them how blessed they are that God is on their side to make things happen. I want them to be a good leader someday.

68. Yes, as a leader, it is important to have enough knowledge and skills to govern its fellow members.

Facial seriousness, because my voice is serious but my face is not. I want to improve it.

69. Yes, for me as one of the officers of this organization, the leadership skills that I need to enhance is to invite other youth that are not active in church. In that way, we can

- help one another and improve more in physical, mental, emotional, and spiritual aspects.
- The particular leadership skill that I want to develop more is the knowledge with the organization involved with, so that I would know all the church activities and solve problems that will be encountered.
70. Yes, because we need to develop our strong ties and friendship as brothers and sisters in Christ.
- To be a responsible leader, because if you are a good and responsible leader, you can influence other members to follow you and lead them to the right path.
71. Yes, as an officer, you need to have a good leadership skills because you are the one who will lead the group and it is your responsibility. Also to make the work easier.
- Social manner & behavior, collaboration and courage. To make the work easier and better.
72. Yes, the greater the leader, the greater the organization.
- Good listener/follower, a good leader is a good follower.
73. Yes, to develop their skills more for better leadership.
- Conflict resolution. To have a better approach on problem solving.
74. Yes, to improve our skills as a UMYF officers and leaders.
- Team work, because I will make the dream works.
75. Yes, to improve the skills of every youth in a church or in a community. Also, to build their confidence in leading others to know God and to make Him known.

I want to develop my communication skills and leadership abilities because I am an introvert person. I want to develop these to be a better servant of God and to serve others the way I should.

76. Yes, in order for each of us to be highly equipped in any obstacles encountered.

Execution and implementation, because in order to be an effective leader, there must be a successful output and not just planning only. For leaders must act.

77. As a UMYF officer/leader, I think that there is a need for leadership skills enhancement, because we can be better if we have leadership skill.

The leadership skill I wish to develop is time management, because it is very important that I manage my time.

78. Yes, to improve leadership skills.

Guiding other people, because I cannot handle them.

79. Yes, leadership skills enhancement is very important for us as an officer and leader.

Spiritual formation in terms of church ministry, because I know that my skills is not enough.

80. As a leader, I think there is a need for leadership skills enhancement. According to John Maxwell, he wrote a book entitled *The 21 Irrefutable Laws of Leadership*, there he said that leadership develops daily, not in a day (No. 3 Law of Process) which means as a leader, we need a continuous learning and training.

The fluency and proficiency in speaking. Because as a leader, I think it is one of the most important skills a leader must have.

81. Yes, based on my experience as a youth leader, there's a need for an aspiring leaders/youth to take a leadership skills enhancement program to become an effective model.

Being a charismatic person, it is because you can easily influence one's life and help him/her grow to be at its fullest as he/she can be.

82. Yes. For them to develop their leadership skill, and leadership skills enhancement will lead the leader towards their vision and missions.

Learning to manage my time, because it is one of my weaknesses.

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EDUCATION

BS Mechanical Engineering, Saint Louis University, 2012

Registered Mechanical Engineer (License no. 0079809)
Professional Regulation Commission (PRC)

WORK EXPERIENCE

Local Licensed Pastor (UMC), 2018 – present

Student Pastor at Wesley Divinity School, MACE II
Admin. Pastor at Bethel UMC, Cabaruan, Sto. Tomas, La Union

Candidate to the Ministry (UMC), 2017-2018

Student Pastor at Wesley Divinity School, MACE I
Campus Minister at Pangasinan State University, Urdaneta City

Draft Engineer, July 2013 to February 2014

Genuino Ice Co., Inc.
817 E. Rodriguez Sr. Boulevard, Quezon City

Mechanical Cadet Engineer, April to July 2013

Loadstar Shipping Co., Inc.
1294 Romualdez St. Paco, Metro Manila

LEADERSHIP EXPERIENCE

Vice President, 2014 - 2016

United Methodist Young Adult Fellowship
Northwest Philippines Annual Conference

President, 2014 - 2017

United Methodist Young Adult Fellowship

Northeast Pangasinan District

President, 2012 – 2014

United Methodist Youth Fellowship
Northwest Philippines Annual Conference

Finance Department Head, 2010 – 2012

United Methodist Youth Fellowship
Northeast Pangasinan District

Vice President, 2008 – 2010

United Methodist Youth Fellowship
Northeast Pangasinan District

Organization Department Head, 2006 – 2008

United Methodist Youth Fellowship
Northeast Pangasinan District

President, 2005 – 2006

United Methodist Youth Fellowship
Urdaneta United Methodist Church

TRAINING/SEMINAR

Collegiate Campus Ministry, Baguio Episcopal Area, January 2017

Young Leader's Summit, Young People's Ministry, November 2016

Business, Financial, and Leadership Training, USANA PH, 2013-2016

The Proper Installation of Plant Mechanical and Electrical Rotating Equipment Using Shaft Alignment, Petro Era One, November 2011

RELEVANT SKILLS

- Business, Finance, and Leadership Management
- Intra and Interpersonal skills